

Shortcomings in the Cochrane review on zinc and the common cold by Nault et al. (2024)

Harri Hemilä, MD, PhD

Department of Public Health, University of Helsinki, Helsinki, Finland

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4710-307X>

<https://loop.frontiersin.org/people/866706>

<https://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.uri?authorId=56223570700>

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/?term=hemila+zinc>

<https://www.mv.helsinki.fi/home/hemila/zinc.htm>

2024-9-14

Available at:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13762570>

Summary

Over a dozen placebo-controlled trials have examined the effects of zinc lozenges on common cold symptoms. Several meta-analyses of the trials with different statistical approaches have demonstrated strong evidence that properly composed zinc lozenges can shorten the duration of colds. A Cochrane review on zinc for the common cold was published in 2013; however, it was withdrawn because of data plagiarism. In 2024, a new Cochrane review was published on zinc for the common cold. The review concluded that “On the basis of this review, the current evidence is insufficient to provide firm conclusions or recommend zinc supplementation for the prevention or treatment of the common cold”. This conclusion is substantially different from many other meta-analyses which have indicated benefit. Therefore, I critically appraised the new Cochrane review (2024) and describe here several concerns which explain the different conclusions. There are errors in the inclusion and exclusion of randomized trials, and in data extraction and statistical analysis in the Cochrane review (2024). The Cochrane review authors consider that zinc lozenges are a form of dietary supplement; however, the effect of zinc lozenges is local and not explained by effects caused by ingestion. The analysis of adverse effects is misleading; based on the literature, it seems highly unlikely that the dosage used in controlled trials, 80–92 mg/day of zinc for 1-2 weeks, would cause severe adverse effects. In conclusion, the Cochrane review (2024) is not an adequate analysis of the available data on zinc lozenges for the common cold.

Contents	Page
Strong evidence that properly composed zinc lozenges can shorten the duration of colds	3
Flaws in the preceding Cochrane review (2011/2013/2015) on zinc for the common cold	4
Conclusion of Cochrane review (2024) on therapeutic zinc for the common cold	5
Revision of Nault’s main meta-analysis on zinc treatment of common cold duration	6
Pharmacology of zinc lozenges is not considered in the Cochrane review (2024)	11
Zinc lozenges are not all equal: many lozenges are ineffective	14
Inclusion of flawed trials, and trials inconsistent with inclusion criteria	18
Ignoring a 48-fold variation in zinc dosage in the nasal administration trials	23
Unsound subgroup comparison by zinc dosage and by the type of zinc salt	26
Analysis of ongoing colds at the end of the follow-up is a statistically unsound approach	28
Experimental colds and natural colds should not be pooled in the same meta-analyses	30
Misunderstandings about RCT methods in the Risk of Bias (RoB) assessment	32
Analysis of adverse effects is not appropriate	37
PICO criteria were not considered in the Cochrane review (2024)	43
Potential explanations for the negative results in the Hemilä (2020) trial were ignored	46
Misleading Background section	48
Practical implications and guidance for further research	49
Flaws in data extraction	52
Errors in other Cochrane reviews	57
References	59

Strong evidence that properly composed zinc lozenges can shorten the duration of colds

Over one dozen randomized trials (RCTs) have examined the effects of zinc lozenges on the duration of the common cold. The findings have been variable, however there is a plausible explanation for the heterogeneity. Eby demonstrated that a substantial proportion of the variation in the results can be explained by the amount of free zinc ions released from the zinc lozenges in that low levels of free zinc ions explained negative findings, and high levels of free zinc ions explained positive findings [1-5]. Bakar also showed that the level of free zinc ions closely correlated with the observed efficacy of zinc lozenges [6].

Ebys's analyses, based on solution chemistry, are informative. However, the impact of zinc dosage level can also be seen in a simple analysis by the total zinc dosage. There has been more than a 7-fold variation in the daily dose of elemental zinc in the zinc lozenge trials. In 2011, I showed that 5 RCTs that used low doses of zinc (<75 mg/day elemental Zn) uniformly found no benefit from zinc lozenges. In contrast, 3 trials used zinc acetate in daily doses of ≥ 75 mg elemental Zn and the pooled result indicated a 42% (95% CI: 35-48%) reduction in the duration of colds [7]. Five trials used zinc gluconate in daily doses of ≥ 75 mg, and colds were shortened on average by 20% (95% CI: 12-28%) [7]. Although the point estimate of effect was quite different for acetate and gluconate salts in the 2011 analysis, a further meta-analysis directly comparing trials of zinc acetate lozenges with trials of zinc gluconate lozenges did not demonstrate a significant difference [8]. The pooled estimate from 7 trials of acetate and gluconate salts with zinc dose ≥ 75 mg/day indicated that common colds were shortened on average by 33% (95% CI: 21-45%; $P = 0.000\ 000\ 05 = 10^{-7}$) [8]. Such a very narrow confidence interval – as also indicated by the P-value – is very strong evidence that properly formulated zinc lozenges can reduce the duration of colds.

Because the evidence for zinc acetate lozenges was stronger, the findings of the zinc acetate lozenge trials were analyzed further. In an Individual Patient Data (IPD) meta-analysis, colds were shortened by 36-40% (2.7-day reduction for the average of 7-day colds in the placebo group), and the effect of zinc acetate lozenges was not modified by age, gender, ethnic group, allergy status, smoking, or baseline severity of the common cold [9]. In another IPD meta-analysis using Cox regression, zinc acetate lozenges increased the recovery rate from colds by rate ratio (RR) = 3.1 [10]. Based on data available for 3 zinc gluconate trials the increase in recovery rate was by RR about 2 to 3 [10].

Zinc lozenges are dissolved in the oropharyngeal region, thus it is possible there are differences in the size of the effect of zinc lozenges on the duration of pharyngeal symptoms compared with nasal symptoms. However, a meta-analysis of the 3 zinc acetate lozenge trials did not find substantial differences in the effects on various respiratory symptoms. Zinc acetate lozenges shortened the duration of nasal discharge on average by 34%, nasal congestion by 37%, sneezing by 22%, scratchy throat by 33%, sore throat by 18%, hoarseness by 43%, and cough by 46% [11]. Muscle ache was shortened by 54%.

The quantile treatment effect (QTE) analysis of the 3 zinc acetate lozenge trials firmly demonstrated that the average treatment effect (ATE) of 2.7 days [9] was inconsistent with the effects on short and long colds. The ATE exaggerates the effect on short colds, and underestimates the effect on long colds [12-14]. The QTE analysis shows that the relative scale much better captures the effect of zinc acetate lozenges, hence the 36% reduction in common cold duration is a more useful estimate for the effect of zinc acetate lozenges than the 2.7-day reduction in duration [12,14].

Flaws in the preceding Cochrane review (2011/2013/2015) on zinc for the common cold

Cochrane reviews are often promoted as high-quality systematic reviews that can be trusted:

“Cochrane: Trusted evidence. Informed decisions. Better health.”

<https://www.cochrane.org> (Accessed 2024-9-13).

In 2011, I found that there were severe errors in the Cochrane review “*Zinc for the common cold*” (2011) [15]. I provided formal feedback in which I pointed out several flaws and encouraged the authors to correct them [16]. However, when the next version of the Cochrane review was published in 2013 [17], almost all the errors remained. In the 2023 version, there also seemed to be plagiarism of text and data from another article as documented in a separate report [18]. Unfortunately, the editors of the Cochrane Acute Respiratory Infections group had not checked that the flaws demonstrated in 2011 were corrected in the 2013 revision. Eventually, this process ended with the withdrawal of that Cochrane review “*Zinc for the common cold*” in 2015:

Hemilä identified multiple errors in this Cochrane Review and made allegations of plagiarism of text and data from a previously published systematic review... The Editor in Chief carried out further investigation into the alleged plagiarism of data, with the cooperation of the review authors, who provided supplementary information in support of their work. The allegations related to the derivation of means and standard deviations of data from some of the included studies. Although the authors acknowledge and cite the Hemilä 2011 review, the Editor in Chief considered that the authors’ explanation regarding some similarities in presented data between the two reviews was not conclusive. This version of the review will therefore remain withdrawn [19].

As a result of the withdrawal of the Cochrane review on zinc for the common cold (2013), the associated JAMA Clinical Evidence Synopsis was also retracted [20-22].

Interestingly, the first author of the Cochrane zinc for the common cold review [15,17,19], which was withdrawn because of plagiarism, still serves as an editor of the Cochrane Acute Respiratory Infections group despite violating publication ethics:

“*Contact Editors: Dr Meenu Singh, India*” <https://ari.cochrane.org/contact-us> (2024-9-10).

There are also flaws in certain other Cochrane reviews; see the last section of this document.

Conclusion of Cochrane review (2024) on therapeutic zinc for the common cold

A new Cochrane review on zinc for the common cold by Nault et al. was published in 2024 [23]. The conclusions for treatment of the common cold were rather negative:

On the basis of this review, the current evidence is insufficient to provide firm conclusions or recommend zinc supplementation for the prevention or treatment of the common cold.

[23, p.28: Implications for practice].

This was based on Nault's calculation in Analysis 9.1 [23, p.163], which led to the estimated effect:

When zinc is used for cold treatment, there may be a reduction in the mean duration of the cold in days (MD -2.37, 95% CI -4.21 to -0.53; $I^2 = 97%$; 8 studies...

[23, p.2: Abstract].

This estimate has a much wider confidence interval than the above-described estimate [8] (see above), which indicates that the efficacy of zinc may be doubtful.

However, there are numerous shortcomings in the Cochrane (2024) meta-analysis on zinc and the common cold by Nault [23]. This document describes the shortcomings.

Revision of Nault's main meta-analysis on zinc treatment of common cold duration

There are 4 major shortcomings in Nault's analysis of zinc for treating the common cold.

First, in the general community there is a large variation in the duration of colds, which can last for 1 day to 3 weeks and over. Obviously, the 1-day colds cannot be shortened by the 2.37 days calculated by Nault. Thus, the "2.37-day" ATE [23] is not applicable over the wide variation in cold duration. Furthermore, given the ATE of 2.37 days, and the impossibility of 1-day colds to be shortened by more than 1 day, it is obvious that the effect of zinc lozenges must be greater on some colds that are longer than 2.37 days. This is demonstrated with the QTE analysis [12-14]. Previously, it has been shown that the relative scale much better captures the effect of treatments on many continuous outcomes such as the duration of colds [12-14,24-28]. Therefore, the relative scale (percentage) was used in our Cochrane review on vitamin C and the common cold in the 2004 [29], 2007 [30,31] and 2013 versions [32]. The relative scale estimate is applicable to the 1-day colds as well as to the 3-week colds. Meta-analysis on the percentage effect scale can be done easily in the Cochrane RevMan program [29,30,32].

Second, Nault writes that:

We undertook meta-analyses only where meaningful, that is, if the treatments, participants, and the underlying clinical question(s) were similar enough for pooling to make sense. Because the likely mechanisms and potential adverse effects of oral and intranasal zinc differ, we analysed trials of oral zinc (including tablets, capsules, syrups, or lozenges) separately from trials of intranasal zinc (including sprays or gels). If statistical pooling was not appropriate, we produced a narrative summary [23, p.10].

We pooled data from studies that we judged to be clinically homogeneous [23, p.11].

However, in the calculation of the above-mentioned 2.37-day ATE, Nault pooled 3 trials that administered zinc nasally [33-35] with 5 trials that administered zinc as lozenges [36-40], see Figure 1. The two treatments are not similar enough for pooling to make sense because administering zinc to different anatomical regions might cause different effects. Pooling the zinc lozenge trials with nasal zinc trials in Analysis 9.1 is particularly strange since Nault writes in the Methods section that they did not pool, see the text above. Given that there are 10 authors in the Cochrane review [23], it is surprising that none of them picked up this inconsistency between the reporting of methods and the actual methods.

Furthermore, there has been concern over decades that nasal zinc administration may cause long-lasting or permanent anosmia in some patients [41-44]. This concern is also mentioned by Nault [23, p.8], though not properly discussed. Therefore, nasal administration of zinc is not appropriate and estimating the effect of nasal zinc administration is irrelevant unless it emerges that the concerns are unfounded. No concerns about anosmia have been expressed about the administration of zinc lozenges.

Finally, in Analysis 9.1, the lowest zinc dose is 0.044 mg/day [34] while the highest zinc dose is 190 mg/day [36]; see Figure 1. When the intervention dose differs by a factor of 4300 the trials are not "similar enough".

Analysis 9.1. Comparison 9: Mean duration of colds defined by each study) - treatment, Outcome 1: Mean

Study or Subgroup	Zinc			Placebo			V
	Mean	SD	Total	Mean	SD	Total	
Belongia 2001	7	4.5	81	7.3	2.2	79	
Godfrey 1992	4.86	2.7	35	6.13	2.7	38	
Hirt 2000	2.3	0.9	108	9	2.5	105	
Macknin 1998	8.7	8.5	124	8.7	2.8	125	
Mossad 2003	4.1	2.3	40	6.5	2.7	38	
Petrus 1998	3.8	1.44222051	52	5.1	2.8	49	
Prasad 2000	4.5	1.6	25	8.1	1.8	23	
Prasad 2008	4	1.04	25	7.12	1.26	25	
Total (95% CI)			490			482	

Nasal zinc (points to Belongia 2001, Godfrey 1992, Hirt 2000)

Others zinc lozenges (points to Macknin 1998, Mossad 2003, Petrus 1998, Prasad 2000, Prasad 2008)

Analysis 9.1. Comparison 9: Mean duration of colds defined by each study) - treatment, Outcome 1: Mean

Study or Subgroup	Zinc			Placebo			V
	Mean	SD	Total	Mean	SD	Total	
Belongia 2001	7	4.5	81	7.3	2.2	79	
Godfrey 1992	4.86	2.7	35	6.13	2.7	38	
Hirt 2000	2.3	0.9	108	9	2.5	105	
Macknin 1998	8.7	8.5	124	8.7	2.8	125	
Mossad 2003	4.1	2.3	40	6.5	2.7	38	
Petrus 1998	3.8	1.44222051	52	5.1	2.8	49	
Prasad 2000	4.5	1.6	25	8.1	1.8	23	
Prasad 2008	4	1.04	25	7.12	1.26	25	
Total (95% CI)			490			482	

0.044 mg/day (points to Belongia 2001)

190 mg/day (points to Godfrey 1992)

Figure 1. Nault’s Analysis 9.1.: Mean duration of colds (measured in days from start to resolution of the cold, as defined by each study) - **treatment**, Outcome 1: **Mean duration of colds/URTIs (treatment): primary analysis.**

Upper: 3 of the included trials were nasal zinc trials, and 5 were zinc lozenge trials.
 Lower: the lowest dose of zinc was 0.044 mg/day, and the highest dose was 190 mg/day.

Third, Nault does not include the Mossad (1996) trial [45] in Analysis 9.1. Nault includes the Mossad (1996) trial in a dozen other Analyses (10.1, 14.1, 14.2, 14.3, 14.4, 14.6, 14.7, 14.8, 14.10, 14.11, 14.12, 14.13), which implies that Nault has no concerns with the trial methods. Mossad (1996) reported the duration of colds as survival curves. The IPD can be extracted from the curves and thereby the mean and SD can be calculated. That has been published previously, so the mean and the SD were available [7,8,12,27]. Nevertheless, calculating the means and SDs is straight forward. Nault does not give any explanation for the exclusion of the Mossad (1996) trial from the main analysis on treating the common cold (Analysis 9.1). This exclusion of the Mossad (1996) trial from Analysis 9.1 is inconsistent with the Methods section which states that missing data were imputed:

If numerical outcome data were missing, such as standard deviations (SD) or correlation coefficients, and we were unable to obtain these from the trial authors, we calculated them from other available statistics... [23, p.11]

Fourth, one of the zinc lozenge trials included in the calculation of the 2.37 day ATE was carried out with children: Macknin (1998) [38]. Nault does not discuss potential issues with trials in children. In some vitamin C and common cold trials there was strong evidence that children and adolescents switched their tablets [46,47]. Therefore, common cold trials with children are not as reliable as trials with adults. In addition, there can be differences in the size of the effect between adults and children. Consequently, adults and children were separated in the Cochrane reviews on vitamin C for the common cold [29,30,32].

I revised the meta-analysis corresponding to Nault's Analysis 9.1 by including only the zinc lozenge trials, adding the Mossad (1996) trial, and using the relative scale. I calculated that zinc lozenges shortened colds in adults by 37% (95% CI: 27-46%; $P = 0.000\ 000\ 0007 = 10^{-9}$); Figure 2.

Thus, with the above-justified modifications, using the data that Nault collected, the calculated estimate provides very strong evidence that zinc lozenges can shorten common colds in adults. This is consistent with the previous statistical analyses [1-14].

Inclusion of the trial with children (median age 13) (Macknin 1998) [38] has a minimal effect on the estimate (Figure 2). However, there is a highly significant difference between the 5 adult trials and the Macknin (1998) trial with children ($P = 0.0001$). Therefore, it is most informative to keep the adult and child trials separate. So far there is no evidence that zinc lozenges have an effect on the duration of colds in children. Nault writes in the Methods that:

We considered the following factors to be potential causes of heterogeneity in the effects of the intervention: ... the age (children, adults, elderly) of participants

However, Nault did not separate the Macknin (1998) trial from the adult trials with zinc lozenges. Investigation would have revealed that there is significant heterogeneity between adult and child trials (Figure 2).

Thus, the 5 adult trials with zinc lozenges lead to a conclusion that properly composed zinc acetate and zinc gluconate lozenges can shorten common cold duration in adults by 37% on average.

Figure 2. Pooling the zinc lozenge trials included in Nault’s Cochrane review [23]. The child trial by Macknin (1998) is significantly inconsistent with the 5 trials with adults. Based on the ratio of means estimate [25], zinc lozenges shortened colds in adults by 37% (95% CI: 27-46%; $P = 10^{-9}$). The data are from [23], except for the Mossad (1996) trial, which are from [27]. The included trials were pooled with the *metagen* function of the R package *meta* [48-50], using the inverse variance, random effects options. ROM, ratio of means [25]; RoM = 1.0 indicates that the mean duration of colds is identical in the intervention and control groups.

The zinc acetate and zinc gluconate lozenge trials can also be compared against each other; see Figure 3. In this analysis, there is no indication that the 2 types of lozenges differ ($P = 0.64$ for test of subgroup difference). Nevertheless, the evidence for the efficacy of zinc acetate lozenges is much stronger as indicated by the much narrower confidence interval and the much smaller P-value. Thus, there is more confidence in stating that zinc acetate lozenges are effective than in stating that zinc gluconate lozenges are effective.

Figure 3. Comparison of the adult trials on zinc acetate and zinc gluconate lozenges included in Nault’s Cochrane review [23]. Although there is no evidence that the 2 types of lozenges differ ($P = 0.64$), the evidence is much stronger for zinc acetate lozenges because of the narrower confidence interval compared with that of zinc gluconate lozenges. Data and methods, see Fig. 2.

Pharmacology of zinc lozenges is not considered in the Cochrane review (2024)

Nault does not discuss the pharmacology of zinc lozenges [23].

In the Abstract: “*There are no established interventions to prevent colds or shorten their duration. However, **zinc supplements** are commonly recommended and taken for this purpose*” [23, p.1]. [Bold added here and in the following excerpts.]

In the Plain Language Summary: “*Key messages: For people who already have a cold, there may be a reduction in how long the cold lasts with **zinc supplements** compared to placebo*” [23, p.2].

In the Background: “*Zinc is naturally present in some foods (e.g. red meat), is sometimes added to other foods (e.g. zinc fortified cereals), and may be taken as **an over-the-counter dietary supplement**...*

***Zinc supplements** exist in several forms, including zinc gluconate, zinc sulfate, zinc acetate, zinc carnosine, and zinc picolinate, which vary in percentage of elemental zinc...*

***Zinc is a popular supplement** often recommended to reduce the duration of the common cold”* [23, p.8].

The term “dietary supplement” indicates that the goal is to increase the nutritional dose, such as supplementation of vitamin D or iron, etc., to increase total daily intake and body levels.

The term “dietary supplement” is described by NIH as follows [51]:

- “As defined by Congress in the Dietary Supplement Health and Education Act, which became law in 1994, **a dietary supplement** is a product (other than tobacco) that
- 1) **is intended to supplement the diet,**
 - 2) contains one or more dietary ingredients (including vitamins, minerals, herbs or other botanicals, amino acids, and other substances) or their constituents,
 - 3) **is intended to be taken by mouth** as a pill, capsule, tablet, or liquid,
 - 4) is labeled on the front panel as being a dietary supplement”.

The FDA states [52]:

What is a **dietary supplement**? ...

A dietary supplement is **a product intended for ingestion** that, among other requirements, contains a "dietary ingredient" **intended to supplement the diet**.

There is no evidence that the effects of zinc lozenges and nasal zinc occur through increased levels of zinc in the body as “dietary supplements”. Moreover, nasal zinc administration in particular is not “intended to be taken by mouth” or “a product intended for ingestion”. Thus, Nault misleads readers by stating that zinc lozenges and nasal zinc are forms of “dietary supplementation”.

The background of the zinc lozenge field is important when considering what types of trials are meaningful and what types of treatments can be pooled reasonably.

In brief, the interest in zinc lozenges (as tablets that are intended to be dissolved slowly in the mouth) for the treatment of the common cold started from the serendipitous observation that the cold symptoms of a 3-year-old girl with leukemia disappeared within a few hours when she slowly dissolved a therapeutic zinc tablet in her mouth instead of swallowing it [1-5,53]. The benefit appeared to be derived from dissolving the tablet in the mouth, which implied that zinc may have local effects in the oropharyngeal region. This observation led the father of the

child, George Eby, to conduct the first RCT on the topic, and he found that zinc gluconate lozenges significantly shortened colds [53].

Given the positive findings in the Eby (1984) trial, Farr (1987) aimed to repeat the study but the findings were different [54]. As an explanation for the inconsistency in the 2 RCTs, Godfrey [55] and Eby [56] pointed out that Farr's lozenges contained 2% citric acid, and in neutral solution citrate and zinc bind together very tightly, so they argued that no free zinc ions were released in the oropharyngeal region from Farr's zinc lozenges.

In the series of correspondence in the journal, Martin published curves for the proportion of free zinc ions and zinc-citrate complexes over the pH range, see Figure 4 [57]. Martin assumed that the pH of saliva was 2.3 after the citric acid-containing lozenges were dissolved, and from the curves he argued that the proportion of free zinc ions would be substantial (Figure 4). However, Zarembo and Godfrey showed in an empirical study with 18 participants that after a lozenge containing 2% citric acid was dissolved in participants' mouths the pH of saliva was on average 4.14, ranging from 3.2 to 5.0 [58]. At such high pH levels, Martin's curve shows that there are few free zinc ions available (Figure 4).

Furthermore, it is also possible that the pH at the mucosa surface is closer to the physiological pH even if the bulk of saliva has pH 4.14. Thus, close to the cell surface layer the concentration of free zinc ions might be even lower than indicated by the pH 4.14 in bulk saliva. This line of reasoning was extended in Eby's reviews [1-4] and Handbook [5].

If the goal is to increase the level of zinc in the body through absorption in the intestines as "dietary supplementation", the composition of the lozenge is largely irrelevant, since the high acidity in the stomach (i.e. low pH ~2) releases free zinc from the zinc-citrate complexes (Figure 4). The zinc in the lozenges eventually enters the stomach, and if the effects of zinc lozenges were through "dietary supplementation", the relationship between the type of lozenge and the efficacy found by Eby [1-5] and Bakar [6] would not be demonstrated.

Furthermore, the doses of zinc used in the nasal administration were very low. The Mossad (2003) dose of 2.1 mg/day of zinc [35] does not constitute a meaningful increase in daily intake. In comparison, the recommended zinc intake in the USA is 11 mg/day for men, and 8 mg/day for women [59]. The Mossad (2003) dose of 2.1 mg/day of zinc is 1/40th of the zinc level in four trials which found benefits from zinc lozenges [37,39,40,45]. The benefit of nasal zinc administration is a particularly strong argument against the notion that zinc functions in all zinc trials as a "dietary supplement".

If the effects of nasal zinc administration and zinc lozenges are local, which is the most reasonable conception of zinc lozenges [1-6], then the proper formulation of lozenges is essential.

These aspects of zinc lozenge pharmacology are missing from Nault's Cochrane review, and there are no references to Eby's reviews [1-4], although he has been by far the most important researcher in the field of zinc lozenges ever since he started the field in 1984 [53].

If the goal of a statistical analysis is to estimate the effects of free zinc ions in the oropharyngeal region on the duration of common colds, several of the published trials on zinc lozenges are irrelevant for reasons similar to those discussed above; see next section.

Figure 4. The proportion of zinc as free zinc ions (Zn^{2+}) and as complexes with citric acid (ZnLH , ZnL^1 , ZnL_2^{4-}) over the pH range. Martin (1988) assumed that after dissolving the 2% citric acid-containing zinc lozenge, the pH of saliva might be 2.3 [57]. However, in an experimental study with 18 participants, Zarembo (1992) showed that, on average, the pH of saliva was 4.14 after the 2% citric acid-containing zinc lozenge was dissolved in participants' mouths [58]. Martin's curve of free Zn^{2+} shows that there are barely any free zinc ions at such high pH. This figure is based on the figure in [57].

Zinc lozenges are not all equal: many zinc lozenges are ineffective

If we administer 0.5 gram tablets of vitamin C from 2 different companies to participants in 2 different RCTs, we do not consider that the interventions substantially differ between the 2 RCTs. However, this is not the case with zinc lozenges, as already described above.

In this section, I describe problems with zinc lozenges in certain trials.

Farr (1987) [54] The lozenge contained 2% citric acid.

See the previous section on pharmacology of zinc lozenges above, and refs. [1-6,55-58].

Nault includes the Farr (1987) trial in Analysis 1.1 [23, p.154]; however, does not refer to the published problems of the zinc lozenge in that trial.

Douglas (1987) [60] The lozenge contained tartaric acid and sodium bicarbonate.

Godfrey [55] pointed out that “*The effervescent tablets [60] contained bicarbonate and an excess of tartaric acid (private communication), which produces a similar result*” as the citric acid in the Farr (1987) trial. Godfrey continued [55]:

Zinc gluconate is less stable than the citrate and tartrate complexes by orders of magnitude, readily giving Zn^+ (gluconate) plus gluconate ion in water. In all likelihood, previous studies [54,60] were done with formulations in which the zinc was not only completely inactivated by complexation but carried a negative charge as well, which would tend to drive it away from inflamed tissues and probably from viral surfaces.

Eby [4] wrote about the problems with Douglas’ lozenges:

The Douglas et al. 1987 RCT report omitted mention of additive food acids in their ‘effervescent’ zinc acetate lozenges... A letter from the lozenge designer and manufacturer, Faulding LTD, Adelaide, South Australia, indicated that the lozenges contained zinc acetate plus tartaric acid and sodium bicarbonate sufficient to result in strong oral effervescence. Zinc acetate dissociates in the presence of these added ingredients and forms several tightly bound reaction products including zinc carbonate, which is non-soluble and non-ionizable and negatively charged zinc tartrate species.

Failing to refer to the published problems of the lozenges in the Douglas (1987) trial, Nault includes the trial in the text section on zinc for treating common cold [23, p.21-25].

Smith DS (1989) [61] The lozenge contained mannitol/sorbitol.

Hemilä commented [8]

The lozenge of the Smith et al. trial contained mannitol and sorbitol. There is experimental evidence that mannitol and sorbitol bind zinc ions in the presence of saliva, which may explain the negative findings in the Smith et al. trial. Furthermore, Dr Smith was one of the authors of the Godfrey et al. trial, which stated in its introduction (p.235 in [36]) that ‘it has been demonstrated that... mannitol/sorbitol inactivate zinc by chelation in saliva’ and ‘mannitol/sorbitol [zinc lozenge] formulations release no zinc ions when dissolved in the mouth’ referring to the Smith et al. trial. This

indicates that afterwards Dr Smith did not trust the lozenge formulation of his 1989 trial.

The Godfrey, Sloane, **Smith DS**, Turco, Mercer, Godfrey (1992) [36] report in their introduction:

Attempts made to duplicate the success which Eby et al. had in 1984 in reducing the duration of the common cold using zinc gluconate have generally been disappointing, the probable reason being that zinc gluconate was inactivated by additives used to mask its unpleasant taste. It has been demonstrated that of these agents, e.g. citric acid [54], tartaric acid [60], or mannitol/sorbitol [61=Smith et al. (1989)], inactivate zinc by chelation in saliva [55,58]. Unflavoured zinc gluconate and the zinc gluconate – glycine (ZGG) lozenges used in the present study release 90 – 93% of zinc ions [58]; whereas citric acid [54] and mannitol/sorbitol [61=Smith et al. (1989)] formulations release no zinc ions when dissolved in the mouth [58]. If the presence of zinc ions in the mouth is required for an effect on the common cold, chelation of zinc may be the reason why the subsequent studies were unsuccessful. This is further suggested by another study, which found a significant reduction of symptoms when a non-chelating formulation was used [62].

Failing to refer to the published problems of the lozenges in the Smith (1989) trial, Nault includes the trial in the text section on zinc for treating the common cold [23, p.21-23,26].

Turner (2000) [63] Induced colds and natural colds. Three types of zinc lozenges against one type of placebo. There were 4 trial arms for experimental rhinovirus colds and 4 trial arms for natural colds. Thus, there were 8 groups in total in the single report.

One zinc gluconate lozenge was used.

Two zinc acetate lozenges were used, one provided 30 mg/day and another provided 69 mg/day zinc.

Eby [64] described problems with the 2 zinc acetate lozenges of Turner (2000):

As a zinc ion availability (ZIA) consultant for Warner Lambert, I found that the 5 and 11.5 mg zinc lozenges whose formula was reported by Turner et al. [63] had theoretical ZIA values of 12 and 36, respectively. On the basis of ZIA analytical methods reported elsewhere [2], zinc acetate lozenges having these ZIA values (strengths) should have reduced the duration of colds by ~1 and ~2.7 days, respectively. However, hydrogenated palm kernel and cotton seed oils were also constituents of the lozenges, according to the list of ingredients provided with the commercial product (Halls Zinc Defense) marketed by Warner Lambert, which is also the supplier of the zinc acetate lozenge clinical prototypes studied by Turner et al. [63]. At the high temperatures (157°C) used in the manufacture of hard candy, these ingredients react with positively charged zinc ions (Zn^{2+} ions) derived from zinc acetate to yield zinc oleate, stearate, and palmitate waxes, which are incapable of releasing Zn^{2+} ions. Consequently, the ZIA value of the zinc acetate lozenges was 0, and no effect on colds could have been expected or resulted.

...

Attention to these omissions is critical if we wish to learn the effects of treating common colds with zinc lozenges, and if we wish to reconcile the negative report of Turner et al. [63] with the very positive reports of Petrus et al. [37] and Prasad et al. [39]. For example, Prasad et al. [39] showed that 50% of zinc acetate recipients were well in 3.8 days, compared with 7.7 days for 50% of placebo recipients. This duration data corresponds well with other generally accepted data.

In the report by Turner et al. [63], the actual zinc compound exposed to the oral mucosa was not zinc acetate, but nonmiscible fat complexes of zinc. The zinc acetate lozenges were not described as producing a dry or astringent feeling in the mouth; in all cases where the ZIA value is sufficiently high to allow Zn^{2+} ions to shorten the duration and severity of common colds, there has been and there will be a dry or astringent feeling in the mouth. This dry feeling is identical to the “clean” mouth feeling produced by swishing water in the mouth for 30–60 s.

The cumulative effect of the above omissions teaches readers that zinc acetate lozenges in general do not have efficacy against common cold; however, properly made zinc acetate lozenges work very well in reducing the duration of common colds.

Turner did not respond to Eby’s criticism, which means that Eby’s criticism was not challenged. Furthermore, the 30 mg/day dose is particularly low. Finally, the actual usage of lozenges was not reported, and therefore it is not clear whether the actual use of the higher dosage was 69 mg/day or much less.

Failing to cite Eby’s letter [64] or Eby’s reviews describing the problems of Turner’s (2000) zinc acetate lozenges [3,4], Nault includes the Turner (2000) trials with zinc acetate lozenges in Analyses 11.1, 11.2, 11.3, 11.4, 11.5. and in text page 22.

Eby (2006) [65] Zinc orotate lozenges

Eby’s commented [4, p.485]:

Zinc orotate is tightly bound (0 mg iZn [free zinc ions]) and essentially insoluble, and non-soluble compounds do not release iZn... Lozenges were nearly insoluble and required more than 1 h to dissolve in the mouth. This study was the second component of our 1984 clinical trial, and its results were published in 2 mid-90s books, but were not published as a peer reviewed article until 2006.

Nault failed to take this problem into account when including the zinc orotate trial by Eby (2006) in Analyses 10.1, 11.1, 11.4, 11.5. If the goal is to estimate the effect of zinc acetate and/or zinc gluconate lozenges (Figure 3), the Eby (2006) trial is irrelevant.

This field of problems in the composition of lozenges was ignored by Nault. It is not appropriate to pool trials purely on the basis that authors used the term “zinc lozenge”. For complex interventions there needs to be justification to conclude that 2 versions of the intervention are “similar enough for pooling to make sense” [23, p.10].

In addition to the chemical composition of zinc lozenges, there has also been variation in the size of the lozenges and the speed at which they are dissolved in the mouth [4, 66 table 4]. In the two Prasad trials (2000, 2008), the lozenges dissolved in about 30 minutes. In the Al-

Nakib (1987) trial, the lozenges dissolved in about 20 minutes, and in the Petrus (1998) and Eby (1986) trials, in about 15 minutes. In the Hemilä (2020) trial, the lozenges dissolved in 8 minutes, which was considered one potential cause for the lack of benefit in that trial [66].

Although several randomized placebo-controlled double-blind trials have shown that properly composed zinc lozenges can shorten common cold duration (Figures 2 and 3) and [1-14], it is not easy for members of the public to find proper zinc lozenges. In his 2010 review [4], Eby wrote that he had looked at the contents of many dozens of zinc lozenges in the US market [4, 67]:

Lack of regulatory review through use of homeopathic laws and dietary supplement regulations of the United States – even though throat lozenges are not allowed under the United States Dietary Supplement Health and Education Act of 1994 – has resulted in commercialization of zinc lozenges that are poorly effective to non-effective...

A 2008 cold-season market survey by this author of zinc lozenges found in national chain stores in Austin, Texas, USA, showed that none met the criteria of high iZn content and long dissolution times, and nearly all released zero iZn...

Most zinc lozenges also contained citric acid...

Some zinc lozenges contained non-ionizable (at pH 7.4) zinc compounds including zinc oxide, aspartate, tartrate, picolinate, orotate and various amino acid chelates, which are believed inefficacious against colds. Choices of zinc compounds that do not release iZn at pH 7.4 are believed predicated on commercial desires to avoid the orally astringent and drying nature of iZn, thus a cure for the common cold is precluded by marketing forces, not science. A current assessment of more than 40 over-the-counter zinc lozenges is maintained on the Internet [not available any more, see copy at [67]]. Zinc lozenges marketed in the United States appear to compete based upon taste rather than efficacy [4, p.490].

Of the 40 different brands of over-the-counter zinc lozenges and many variations of them currently available in the US, very few – based upon this analysis and ingredients listed on their labels – appear to release useful amounts of iZn regardless of total zinc content, and none of them can be considered as a cure for common colds. With several exceptions, nearly all appear likely to have a null effect on colds [4, p.490].

Inclusion of flawed trials, and trials inconsistent with inclusion criteria

In addition to the above-described problems with the zinc lozenge compositions in certain trials, there are other problems in some trials included by Nault [23].

Nault included the Weismann (1990) [68], Kurugöl (2006) [69], Kurugöl (2007) [70], Vakili (2009) [71], Rerksuppaphol (2013) [72], Sánchez (2014) [73], and Somé (2015) [74] trials in the Cochrane review although these also have various issues.

In **Analyses 11.1, 11.2, 11.4**, Nault included the **Weismann (1990)** trial [68].

In the Methods section of the Cochrane review, Nault writes: “*Types of studies: We included randomised controlled trials (RCTs) and excluded studies using quasi-randomisation because they are susceptible to selection bias*” [23, p.8].

However, the Weismann (1990) [68] trial did not use randomization, instead it used alternative allocation. For my first meta-analysis of zinc lozenges, I contacted Kaare Weismann and in the Supplement 2 [7, p.xiii], I documented:

The 1990 study report did not describe the method of allocation. Dr. Kaare Weismann described that they had used consecutive allocation (personal communication by email 2 July 2010).

When Nault’s inclusion criteria strictly require random allocation, a trial should not be included if the allocation method is unclear. Furthermore, when starting a new project on zinc for the common cold, Nault should have read the previous analyses on the same topic and would have found the above information about Weismann’s allocation.

In **Analyses 1.1, 3.1, 4.1, 7.1-7.9, 8.2**, Nault included the **Kurugöl (2006)** trial [69].

Kurugöl reported that the duration of colds was 5.3 (SD 0.7) days in the placebo group and 4.7 (SD 0.8) days in the zinc group, table III in [69]. Nault copies these figures to Cochrane review Analysis 3.1. The weight of the Kurugöl (2006) trial is the greatest in Analysis 3.1, 44.7%, so it is not a minor issue if there are flaws in the Kurugöl data.

The very narrow SD values are not believable. In our Cochrane review we imputed some missing SD values on the basis of estimating the ratio between SD/mean. We wrote [32, p.8]:

Some trials presented the mean duration or severity of colds, but not the respective SD... we estimated SD as identical with the mean of the treatment group. This is based on our analysis that for trials reporting the SD, the ratio of SD to mean is on average 0.7 so that our ratio of 1.0 used in the SD imputation is somewhat conservative. The consequence of this is that we are putting slightly reduced weight in our estimates of effect on these trials with missing SD values, compared to the average.

In the Kurugöl (2006) trial, the SD/mean ratios are 0.13 and 0.17 in the placebo and zinc groups, respectively. This ratio is very small compared with the usual distribution of common cold duration, so the “SD” values are doubtful.

In comparison, Nault Analysis 3.1 also includes the Kartasurya (2012) trial. In that trial, the SD/mean ratios are 0.67 and 0.64 in the placebo and zinc groups, respectively, which are close

to the mean value 0.7 in the large set we analyzed for our Cochrane review on vitamin C and the common cold [32].

Furthermore, Kurugöl's table III reports the SD for total cold symptoms, which is 0.7 days in the placebo group as mentioned above. The table also reports the SD for cough (SD 2.0 days), nasal drainage (SD 1.8 days), nasal congestion (SD 1.0 days). It is not reasonable to assume that the variation in the component symptoms would sum up to the total cold symptoms with less variance than the variance of the component symptoms.

Furthermore, in figure 1, Kurugöl reports total symptom severity scores by day in both the zinc and placebo groups. He calculated that $P = 0.000$ for day 2, although the SE-bars of the two groups substantially overlap. Thus, Kurugöl's statistical analysis is questionable.

I was able to contact Dr. Kurugöl, who sent an email to me on 2015-1-16. However, when I described the problems in the SD values in Kurugöl's 2006 paper and asked whether the data set was still available, there was no response. Therefore the reported SD estimates should not be trusted.

Evidently, a trial should not be included in a meta-analysis, if it is not clear whether the dispersion is reported as SD or SE; or a conservative SD = mean imputation should be used for common cold duration.

Nault included the **Kurugöl (2007)** trial [70] in the text section [23, p.20-25].

The Kurugöl (2007) report does not refer to the Kurugöl (2006) report; see above. This is very strange since the previous zinc trial by the same authors is obviously relevant for the new trial report. The Kurugöl 2007 report has similar problems to the 2006 report.

For example, in figure 1, Kurugöl reports total symptom severity scores by day in the zinc and placebo groups. He calculated that $P = 0.000$ for day 2, although the SE-bars of the two groups substantially overlap. Thus, the statistical analysis is also not trustworthy in the 2007 report.

In **Analyses 2.1, 4.1, 8.2** Nault included the **Vakili (2009)** trial [71]. Vakili reported that the average common cold occurrence was 3.1 (SD 0.55) in the placebo group and 1.7 (SD 0.86) in the zinc group, table 2 in [71].

Events such as the occurrence of colds are usually over-dispersed compared with a Poisson distribution. The Poisson distribution has the relation variance = mean, but for natural events the distribution is usually wider so that variance > mean. Therefore, given the mean = 3.1 in the placebo group, the SD should be ≥ 1.76 . Vakili's SD = 0.55 corresponds to Var = 0.30 which is not believable for a Poisson type outcome with mean 3.1.

Furthermore, Vakili states in the Methods that "*a total of 200 children were randomly assigned to supplementation with 10 mg elemental zinc as a tablet (n = 100, 50 males, and 50 females), or placebo (n = 100, 50 males, and 50 females).*"

However, it is extremely unlikely that random allocation of 200 participants leads to exactly the same number of both sexes within both treatment groups.

Finally, no drop-outs were reported even though 200 children were followed for 5 months. Evidently, in such a large group some drop-outs are to be expected. For all the above reasons the results of the Vakili 2009 trial should be questioned.

In 2018, I tried to contact Dr. Vakili and some of the colleagues whom I was able to identify from PubMed papers on the basis of them being co-authors. I was not successful in contacting Dr. Vakili.

When the published SD is statistically impossible, the trial should not be included in a meta-analysis; or a conservative SD should be imputed.

In the Methods section Nault writes: “*Types of studies: We included randomised controlled trials (RCTs) and excluded studies using quasi-randomisation because they are susceptible to selection bias*” [23, p.8]. However, given the identical distribution of 50 patients in each cell of the 2×2 table by treatment and sex, it seems unlikely that the Vakili (2009) trial was randomized.

In **Analyses 1.1, 3.1, 4.1, 7.1-7.3, 8.1**, Nault included the **Rerksuppaphol (2013)** trial [72].

Rerksuppaphol (2013) randomized 100 children to the zinc and placebo groups using blocks of two. According to their Table 1 [72], the average age was 10.0 yr (SD 0.5 yr) in the zinc group, but 11.4 yr (SD 0.8 yr) in the placebo group. The authors calculated $P = 0.0001$ for the difference in baseline age between the zinc and placebo groups. Consistently, the height was also highly significantly different in the zinc group (135.5 cm) compared with the placebo group (141 cm), with $P = 0.0001$. In their paper, Rerksuppaphol et al. do not propose an explanation for the highly significant imbalance in baseline age; they just write that:

Despite strict randomization and a double blind design, there was an imbalance in the study between the demographic profiles of the two groups. This was most likely because of statistical probability...

This is not a reasonable explanation for a $P = 0.0001$ difference in a baseline variable, particularly for a highly essential variable such as age. If 20 baseline variables are measured in an RCT, and one or two of them give a P-value somewhat less than 0.05 for the baseline difference in a t-test, that is consistent with successful randomization. However, successful randomization is refuted when $P = 0.0001$ for a baseline variable as essential in biology as age.

As their most interesting finding, Rerksuppaphol reported that coughs and runny noses were shorter in the zinc group, with $P = 0.01$. The median duration for cough was 1.0 days in the zinc group, and 6.0 days in the placebo group. The total duration of the trial was 3 months and it seems obvious that many participants had more than 1 cough episode per 3 months. However, the Methods and Results sections do not describe whether the duration of cough means duration per episode or duration per person. Thus the outcomes are not well described.

Differences in cumulative duration of cough can be 1) due to difference in incidence of cough episodes or 2) due to difference in the duration of cough episodes, or 3) due to a combination of both.

Given the reported highly significant baseline imbalance in age and height, and the lack of transparency in the outcomes, it is difficult to trust the reports on coughs and runny noses.

In the RoB table, Nault assigns a “+” mark for the “random sequence generation” indicating that Nault is satisfied with the allocation even though there is published evidence by the authors that the groups were highly significantly biased at baseline with $P = 0.0001$.

Nault describes the findings of the **Sánchez (2014)** trial [73] in the text section [23, p.18]:

Sánchez 2014 found incidence rates of acute respiratory infections (ARI) for those receiving chelated zinc (1.42 per 1000 child-days), zinc sulfate (1.57 per 1000 child-days), and placebo (3.3 per 1000 child-days).

The Sánchez (2014) trial was not an individual-level RCT. Sánchez writes in the abstract: “*Randomized triple-blind community trial with 301 children between 2-5 years of age from six child daycare centers in Medellin, Colombia. Children were distributed in three groups receiving zinc amino acid chelate, zinc sulfate and placebo*” [73].

Allocation is described in figure 1 of [73]. Google Translate gives the following version of the allocation process [original in Spanish]:

Randomization and masking

The six clusters were randomly assigned by means of a ballot so that two children’s centers were in each of the three study groups. One group received zinc sulfate, another group received amino-chelated zinc, and the last group received placebo [73, p.81].

Although 6 units can be “randomized” to 3 groups as $2 + 2 + 2$, it is not reasonable to consider that such “randomization” leads to meaningful baseline similarity. There is no justification to believe that a very small number of observation units are balanced on baseline variables. The prevalence of viruses varies between geographic regions and between social groups, etc. Any differences between a few child daycare centers can be caused by differences between exposures to viruses or other factors.

If the number of units is substantial, then it is reasonable to assume that on average the distributions are similar over the numerous units so that two large groups of units would give similar means if there is no treatment. For example, the Somé (2015) [74] trial included 25 villages, see below. In contrast, the comparison of 2 vs 2 vs 2 childcare centers is not meaningful because of the natural variations in the prevalence of viruses, etc.

Under the title “*Mean number of colds/URTIs developed*”, Nault describes the findings of the **Somé (2015)** [74] trial in the text [23, p.18]. Nault writes:

Somé 2015 reported their longitudinal prevalence for URTI at 7.3 (6.2 to 8.4) and 8.1 (6.9 to 9.3) for the 5 mg and 10 mg zinc groups, respectively, compared with the group who received a placebo tablet’s longitudinal prevalence of 7.5 (6.3 to 8.7).

However, “*longitudinal prevalence*” is not a form of “*mean number of colds/URTIs developed*”.

In their paper, Somé [74] defines:

... longitudinal prevalence as the per cent of total days of observation (or 'recalled' days) on which the disease was present (ie, the numerator is the total number of days with a disease and the denominator is the total number of days of observation).

Differences in "longitudinal prevalence" can be 1) due to difference in incidence of episodes or 2) due to difference in the duration of episodes, or 3) due to a combination of both. In any case, it is not a measure of "Mean number of colds/URTIs developed".

Ignoring a 48-fold variation in zinc dosage in the nasal administration trials

In Analysis 9.1, Nault pools 3 nasal zinc administration trials together with 5 zinc lozenge trials.

In Analysis 9.2.1, Nault pools 3 nasal zinc trials as a separate subgroup. In the latter meta-analysis, there is extreme heterogeneity between the 3 nasal zinc trials with $I^2 = 99\%$. The maximum of the I^2 -heterogeneity scale is 100% and the minimum is 0%, thus the heterogeneity over the 3 nasal zinc trials is extreme. When there is substantial heterogeneity, the goal should be to search for explanations for the heterogeneity, instead of pooling trials which are very different. One evident possibility to explain the extreme heterogeneity in this case is the dose used in the trials, which is not considered by Nault.

Belongia (2001) wrote that the “total maximum daily dose was 0.044 mg elemental zinc” [34, p.104].

Mossad (2003) describes a “total daily dose of elemental zinc of about 2.1 mg” [35, p.37].

Thus, the daily dose of zinc used by Mossad (2003) was 48 (= 2.1/0.044) times greater than the daily dose of zinc used by Belongia (2001). Mossad found a statistically significant reduction in common cold duration of 2.4 days, whereas Belongia found no significant difference between the zinc and placebo groups. An obvious explanation is that the dose used by Belongia was simply so small that no effect is expected. Figure 5 shows the comparison of the 2 trials as a forest plot. Heterogeneity between the 2 trials is very high ($P = 0.0022$).

Figure 5. Comparison of the Belongia (2001) [34] and Mossad (2003) [35] trials in a forest plot on the ratio scale. There is strong evidence that the trials by Belongia (2001) and by Mossad (2003) do not estimate the same treatment effect because the P-value for the test of inconsistency is very small, $P = 0.0022$. The data are from [23]. ROM, ratio of means [25].

Assuming that Mossad’s 2.4-day (37%) reduction in cold duration is a reasonable estimate for the effect of the 2.1 mg/day nasally administered zinc, and assuming a linear dose-response relationship, we can interpolate that the effect of the 0.044 mg/day zinc in the Belongia study should be that colds are 0.05 days (or 0.8%) shorter in the zinc group (2.4 days/48 or

37%/48). Figure 6 shows the relation between dosage and the percentage effect in the two trials. The observed difference between the zinc and placebo groups in the Belongia (2001) trial is consistent with the expected effect.

Figure 6. Dosage of zinc and the difference between the zinc and placebo groups in the nasal zinc administration trials by Belongia (2001) [34] and Mossad (2003) [35]. The red diagonal line indicates interpolation of dose-response assuming linearity with the constraint that the zinc dose of 0 mg/day equals placebo with null effect. The point estimate of the Belongia (2001) trial is very close to the expected null effect. The vertical lines indicate the 95% CI range and the point in the middle is the observed effect. The effect estimates are from Figure 5.

The third nasal zinc trial in Nault’s Analysis 9.1 was Hirt (2000) [33], who reported the volume of zinc gel to both nostrils per day (0.96 mL), but not the concentration of zinc in the gel. In their introduction they state that they intended to repeat an earlier study that administered gel containing 33 mmol/L of elemental zinc. If that was the concentration of Hirt nasal zinc gel, that would lead to zinc dose of 2.06 mg/day. Hirt found significant benefit from zinc, consistent with the Mossad (2003) trial. The Hirt (2000) trial is not included in Figure 6 since the dose is not reported in the paper [33], though it can be assumed.

Naoult wrote:

We undertook meta-analyses only where meaningful, that is, if the treatments, participants, and the underlying clinical question(s) were similar enough for pooling to make sense [23, p.10].

When there is a 48-fold difference in the dosage of a drug in 2 trials, it does not make sense to assume that the interventions are “similar enough”.

Furthermore, Nault writes in Methods [23, p.11]:

We considered the following factors to be potential causes of heterogeneity in the effects of the intervention: ... dose of the zinc intervention ...

However, Nault did not publish any analysis comparable to Figure 6.

Nault also writes [23, p.21]:

When three studies utilising intranasal zinc ... were compared with five studies utilising zinc lozenges ... there was no apparent difference between subgroups ($I^2 = 0\%$; Analysis 9.2).

Here Nault ignores the lack of statistical power in the comparison of the zinc lozenge and nasal zinc trials. The effect estimate in the “intranasal zinc” group is not accurate enough for meaningful comparisons. The 95% CI for the estimate of effect for the nasal zinc group is from -7.36 days to +1.05 days. This means that if the estimate in the zinc lozenge subgroup is within this range, the difference between the point estimates for nasal zinc and zinc lozenges would not be statistically significant. When the estimate of effect within the nasal zinc group is very extreme with $I^2 = 99\%$ (mostly explained by the 48-fold variation in zinc dose), the mean effect for such a group is not a useful basis for the comparison with other kinds of zinc treatments.

Unsound subgroup comparisons by zinc dosage and by the type of zinc salt

In Analysis 9.1, Nault included 3 nasal zinc trials and 5 zinc lozenge trials; see above.

In Analysis 9.3 (Figure 7), Nault carried out a subgroup analysis by zinc dosage of the same 8 trials, using 85 mg/day of zinc as the cut-off limit. In the Results section, Nault describes this comparison [23, p.21]:

When four studies using > 85 mg/day of zinc (Godfrey 1992; Petrus 1998; Prasad 2000; Prasad 2008) were compared with four studies using < 85 mg/day of zinc (Belongia 2001; Hirt 2000; Macknin 1998; Mossad 2003) there was no apparent difference between subgroups ($I^2 = 0\%$; Analysis 9.3).

Analysis 9.3. Comparison 9: Mean duration of colds (measured in days from start to resolution of the cold, as defined by each study) - treatment, Outcome 3: Subgroup analysis (treatment): daily dose of zinc.

Study or Subgroup	Zinc			Placebo		
	Mean	SD	Total	Mean	SD	Total
9.3.1 > 85 mg/d						
Godfrey 1992	4.86	2.7	35	6.13	2.7	38
Petrus 1998	3.8	1.44222051	52	5.1	2.8	49
Prasad 2000	4.5	1.6	25	8.1	1.8	23
Prasad 2008	4	1.04	25	7.12	1.26	25
Subtotal (95% CI)			137			135
Heterogeneity: Tau ² = 1.14; Chi ² = 19.48, df = 3 (P = 0.0002); I ² = 85%						
Test for overall effect: Z = 4.04 (P < 0.0001)						
9.3.2 < 85 mg/d						
Belongia 2001	7	4.5	81	7.3	2.2	79
Hirt 2000	2.3	0.9	108	9	2.5	105
Macknin 1998	8.7	8.5	124	8.7	2.8	125
Mossad 2003	4.1	2.3	40	6.5	2.7	38
Subtotal (95% CI)			353			347

Figure 7: Nault’s Analysis 9.3.: Mean duration of colds (measured in days from start to resolution of the cold, as defined by each study) - treatment, Outcome 3: Subgroup analysis (treatment): daily dose of zinc.

However, Nault ignored the difference in the route of administration and in the type of participants.

The high dose (>85 mg/day) zinc subgroup includes 4 adult zinc lozenge trials.

The low dose (<85 mg/day) zinc subgroup includes 3 nasal zinc trials and 1 child zinc lozenge trial.

Thus, the comparison is mainly a comparison between zinc lozenges vs. nasal zinc administration, and the dosage is just a correlate for the route of administration. Meaningful dose-response analysis should be restricted to one route of administration as in Figure 6.

Furthermore, Nault put the Hirt (2000) [33] nasal zinc administration trial in the “low dose” group although Nault writes of that trial (see also section “Flaws in data extraction”):

“Dose per day (elemental zinc in mg): unclear” [23, p.70]

but at the same time Nault writes of the Hirt (2000) trial:

“Zinc gluconate 960 mg/d nasal gel” [23, p.70]

and

“Approximate zinc dose per day... 2.1 mg/d” [23, p.191]

The first dose (unclear) would exclude the Hirt (2000) trial from Nault’s analysis 9.3, while the second (960 mg/d) would put the Hirt (2000) trial to the high dose subgroup, whereas the third (2.1 mg/d) would put the trial to low dose subgroup.

We may guess that the real dose in Hirt (2000) was less than 85 mg/day, but this emphasizes that the route of administration is more of a primary issue than the dose. It seems unlikely that any nasal zinc administration trial can administer “high doses” (>85 mg/day zinc).

The low dose group also includes the Macknin (1998) [38] zinc lozenge trial with children. As shown above, this trial is significantly inconsistent with the adult trials on zinc lozenges (Figure 2). We do not know whether the difference is caused by children cheating or by different pharmacological responses in children, yet in any case the dose is not the only issue when comparing the Macknin (1998) trial with the 4 adult zinc lozenge trials.

Nault argues that “*there was no apparent difference between subgroups ($I^2 = 0\%$; Analysis 9.3).*” However, in addition to the flaws described above, Nault does not take into account the lack of statistical power in the comparison of the so called “high dose” and “low dose” subgroups. The effect estimate in the “low dose” group is very inaccurate. In the low dose group, the 95% CI for the estimate of effect is from -6.1 days to +1.34 days. This means that if the estimate in the “high dose” subgroup sits anywhere within this wide range, there would be no significant difference between the point estimates.

Finally, there is a calculation error in the dose of Prasad (2000) trial, see section “Flaws in data extraction”. In Analysis 9.3., Nault classifies the Prasad (2000) trial in the “high dose” >85 mg/day subgroup, whereas the correct dose is 79 mg/day and thus the trial should be in the “low dose” <85 mg/day subgroup.

Nault also compared the zinc salts used in the trials and wrote [23, p.21]:

we observed that while acetate and gluconate forms seemed to lower the mean duration of colds by just over two days for those taking zinc compared to placebo, zinc sulfate did not show reductions beyond a half day by comparison.

The only trial in the group of the 8 trials that used zinc sulfate was the Belongia (2001) trial. However, it is not just the type of salt that distinguishes the Belongia trial from the Mossad (2003) trial which used nasal administration and the 5 zinc lozenge trials in the same meta-analysis. As noted above, the zinc dose in the Belongia trial was 1/48th of the zinc dose in the Mossad (2003) trial on nasal zinc gluconate, and 1/4300th of the zinc dose in the Godfrey (1992) trial on zinc gluconate lozenges. It makes no sense to propose that the type of salt – zinc sulfate – is the most likely explanation for the lack of efficacy in the Belongia trial (Figure 6).

Analysis of ongoing colds at the end of the follow-up is a statistically unsound approach

In the abstract, Nault writes [23, p.2]:

it is uncertain whether there is a reduction in the risk of having an ongoing cold at the end of follow-up (RR 0.52, 95% CI 0.21 to 1.27; $I^2 = 65\%$; 5 studies, 357 participants...

This estimate of effect is based on Analysis 10.1. The included trials are shown in Figure 8.

**Analysis 10.1. Comparison 1
days from start to resolution
Outcome 1: Risk of ongoing cold**

Follow-up days	Study or Subgroup	Zinc		Placebo		N
		Events	Total	Events	Total	
7 →	Eby 1984	5	37	15	28	
	Eby 2006	6	16	7	17	
7 →	Godfrey 1992	1	35	8	38	
	Hemilä 2020	12	45	8	42	
18 →	Mossad 1996	0	49	2	50	
	Total (95% CI)		182		175	
	Total events:	24		40		

Figure 8. Nault’s Analysis 10.1.: Risk of cold/URTIs at end of study (measured in days from start to resolution of the cold, as defined by each study) – **treatment**, Outcome 1: **Risk of ongoing cold/URTIs at end of study (treatment):** primary analysis.

The Eby (2006) trial [65] examined zinc orotate lozenges and was carried out in 1984 [4], when there was little understanding of plausible mechanisms of effects by zinc lozenges. Afterwards Eby pointed out that the lozenge was chemically unsound since it did not release free zinc ions, see section “Zinc lozenges are not all equal”. To my knowledge there are no later trials on zinc orotate lozenges. A trial on zinc orotate is irrelevant, if the goal is to estimate the effect of zinc acetate or/and zinc gluconate lozenges. Therefore, the Eby (2006) trial is not relevant in the analysis of treatment effects.

The Hemilä (2020) trial [66] administered zinc lozenges for 5 days, but the follow-up lasted for 10 days. The study found a statistically significant decrease in the rate of recovery in the zinc participants after the 5-day treatment ended which could be caused by the rebound effect so that the discontinuation of the zinc lozenge treatment had a physiological effect in the

harmful direction. Although such an effect by the discontinuation of treatment is consistent with a pharmacological effect, the trial does not give a useful estimate for the effect of functional lozenges and treatment protocols.

In the 3 remaining trials, the duration of follow-up is very different. Eby (1984) terminated follow-up at day 7, whereas Mossad (1996) followed up patients to day 18. Using the outcome at an arbitrary end of the follow-up is statistically unsound. This problem is most evident in the case of the Mossad (1996) trial. There were only 2 patients in the placebo group who had not recovered, and 0 in the zinc group (Figure 8). Such a comparison does not give a meaningful estimate for the effect of the examined zinc lozenge. Most recoveries occur before 2 weeks and therefore the most relevant follow-up period is much before day 18. Mossad (1996) reported the recovery curves for both groups up to day 18. Nault could have extracted the number of patients still sick on day 7. Thereby the analysis of Eby (1986) and Mossad (1998) trials would have been similar.

However, the most informative analysis of recovery in the Eby (1986) and Mossad (1998) trials is by using Cox regression, which takes all the information over the follow-up periods and not just a single arbitrary time point. My previous analysis of both trials gave the following estimates of effect as the increase in the rate of recovery [10, p.4 and Supplement 2]:

Eby (1986) RR = 3.5 (95% CI, 1.8–6.7; P = 0.0001)

Mossad (1996) RR = 2.8 (95% CI, 1.8–4.5; P = 0.000 01)

Godfrey (1992) did not report recovery curve over the follow-up. For this kind of analysis the only useful data are on day 7, when 30 of 35 in zinc lozenge group were recovered, compared with 21 of 38 placebo participants. This gave as the rate of recovery by day 7 [10]:

Godfrey (1992) RR = 1.55 (95% CI, 1.13-2.13)

All these three estimates for the increase in the rate of recovery by zinc gluconate lozenges are quite consistent with the effect calculated for the 3 trials on zinc acetate lozenges [10, Supplement 2, p.5]:

Zinc acetate (3 RCTs) RR = 3.1 (95% CI, 2.1–4.7; P = 0.000 000 02)

Thus, Nault's Analysis 10.1 is statistically unsound and presents a pooled estimate that misleads readers.

Experimental colds and natural colds should not be pooled in the same meta-analyses

In Analysis 1.1, Nault pools together trials with experimental colds and trials with natural colds, which is not appropriate.

A large proportion of common colds in the community are caused by rhinoviruses. Rhinoviruses cause such mild infections that it is ethically possible to infect study participants with rhinoviruses and follow the emergence of symptoms and investigate the biochemical changes during the infections.

Some zinc lozenge trials have used the experimental rhinovirus model to investigate the effectiveness of zinc lozenges. However, the context of experimental colds is different compared with colds occurring in the general community. There is no justification to assume the same effect and therefore the 2 contexts should not be pooled.

In the community, adults have on average 2 colds per year, which corresponds to 0.04 colds per week. However, in experimental rhinovirus infections the incidence is much higher (Table 1). The time range of becoming sick in experimental colds is less than a week after the inoculation, but this may be rounded to 1 week. The median incidence in the experimental colds is 0.61 per week in the placebo groups of the zinc trials included by Nault (Table 1), which is over one magnitude greater than the incidence of the common cold in adults in the general community. The high incidence in experimental colds is caused by the inoculation with high doses of viruses.

Table 1: Incidence of colds in experimental rhinovirus infections, the placebo groups

	Inoculated	Cold symptoms	Proportion
Al-Nakib (1987) [62] RV-2	28	8	29%
Al-Nakib (1987) [62] RV-2	69	12	17%
Farr (1987) [54] RV-39	16	12	75%
Farr (1987) [54] RV-13	20	16	80%
Turner (2000) [63] RV-39	400	273	68%
Turner (2001) [75] RV-23, RV-39	37	20	54%

Because of the very different doses of viruses involved in experimental vs. natural colds, there can be substantial differences in the patho-physiology of the colds in the 2 contexts. In fact, one comparison of experimental vs. natural colds concluded that [76]:

For the past 3 decades, rhinovirus grown in cell culture and used to induce experimental infections has been assumed to produce illness comparable to natural rhinovirus illness. However, no studies have been conducted to compare the characteristics of these two illnesses... the symptoms of nasal obstruction and malaise occurred significantly more often on illness days 1–5 during experimental colds. Also, significant differences were found for days 1–4 for feverishness/fever, days 1–3 for nasal discharge, days 1–2 for sneezing, days 3–5 for sore throat, and day 1 for cough. Some of the latter symptoms occurred more frequently with experimental and some with natural infection.

Another study comparing experimental vs. natural colds concluded that [77]:

The highest mean daily symptom score, rhinorrhea score, and nasal obstruction score in the natural cold subjects were 14.2, 2.1, and 2.5 respectively. In contrast, the highest

mean daily symptom score, rhinorrhea score, and nasal obstruction score in the experimental rhinovirus colds were 9.3, 1.8, and 1.8, respectively ($P < 0.005$ compared to natural colds). Similarly, the highest mean daily mucus weight in the natural colds, 2.9 gms, was significantly higher than in the experimental colds, 2.3 gms ($P = 0.01$)... These results suggest that subjects with natural colds have more severe symptoms than subjects with experimental colds.

Thus, natural colds differ dramatically from experimental colds by the level of exposure to viruses and by symptomatology. Therefore, it is possible that zinc lozenges or nasal zinc administration have different effects on experimental vs. natural colds and it is not appropriate to pool such trials.

Naoult wrote:

We undertook meta-analyses only where meaningful, that is, if the treatments, participants, and the underlying clinical question(s) were similar enough for pooling to make sense [23, p.10].

Experimental colds and natural colds are not similar enough for pooling to make sense.

In our Cochrane review on vitamin C and the common cold (2013) we commented [32, p.9]:

Three laboratory trials... in which volunteers were intentionally exposed to known viruses after vitamin C or placebo administration. As they are qualitatively different from the community-based trials on natural common cold infections, they are not included in the meta-analyses but are presented qualitatively.

Misunderstandings about RCT methods in the Risk of Bias (RoB) assessment

This section considers the validity of conclusions in the RoB assessment [23, p.16-17: figure 3].

Allocation concealment

Nault put a question mark “?” for “allocation concealment (selection bias)” for the following 7 trials: Caesar (2012), Kartasurya (2012), Mossad (2003), Petrus (1998), Smith (1989), Turner (2000) challenge, Turner (2000) natural.

However, the same 7 trials have plus mark “+” (acceptable) on “Blinding of participants and personnel (performance bias): All outcomes” and on “Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias): All outcomes”. This indicates that there is some confusion about what “allocation concealment” means.

In the old literature “double-blind” was used to indicate that both patients and researchers did not know which treatment group the patient was in until the end of the trial. Over time this evolved to describe blinding in more detail. There are usually three aspects: the patient, the person(s) carrying out the intervention, and the person(s) assessing the outcome, and in the ideal case all three parties do not know what the treatment is until the trial ends. That is sometimes described as triple-blind, though mostly the term double-blind is used to indicate complete blinding.

“Allocation concealment” is a much more recent concept arising from the fact that in many studies it is not possible to keep all parties blind until the end of the trial. For example, in surgery it is difficult to carry out a trial that is double-blind until the trial ends. In 1983, Thomas Chalmers showed that there were significant differences in findings depending on whether “the randomization process was blinded” [78]. This caused interest in keeping the allocation stage blinded even if the later stages of a trial cannot be blinded, e.g. in surgery. The name of this concept was later changed to “allocation concealment”.

If Nault is satisfied that there is “Blinding of participants and personnel” and “Blinding of outcome assessment” until the trial ends, then – logically – there must be blinding at all preceding time points during the trial, including the process of allocation. Thus, all 7 trials should have a “+” for allocation concealment.

Random sequence generation

For numerous trials, Nault put a question mark “?” for the item “Random sequence generation (selection bias)” even though the reports state that the trials were randomized.

These trials have “?” on “randomization”

Al-Nakib (1987) “members of each group were randomly allocated to receive zinc gluconate lozenges or placebo” [62]

Eby (1984) “was given to each subject, using a double-blind, random method” [53]

Farr Trial 2 (1987) “In trial 2, 23 subjects were randomly chosen to receive zinc and 22 were randomly chosen to receive placebo” [54]

Petrus (1998) “The subjects of this randomized, double-masked, placebo-controlled study” [37]

Prasad (2000) “A research consultant prepared the randomization code and the packages of medication” [39]

Prasad (2008) “A research consultant prepared the randomization code and the packages of medication” [40]

Smith (1989) “Upon enrollment, subjects were randomly assigned to receive either zinc gluconate or placebo” [61]

Turner (2000) natural “were randomized to receive 1 of the 3 treatments” [63]

Turner (2001) “Volunteers were randomly assigned to receive either the active preparation or placebo” [75]

The trials above with the question mark “?” can be compared with trials that have a “+”.

These trials have “+” on “randomization”

Belongia (2001) “The active and placebo nasal spray bottles were randomly placed in blocks of four by the manufacturer” [34]

Douglas (1987) “either zinc acetate or placebo randomly allocated to the sequence” [60]

Farr Trial 1 (1987) “were assigned by prior computer randomization to receive either zinc gluconate or placebo lozenge therapy in trial 1” [54]

Godfrey (1992) “Randomization by a third party was used to assign the 87 participants to treatment groups” [36]

Kurugöl (2006) “A statistical consultant programmed a computer-generated randomization code and prepared the packages of medication” [69]

Kurugöl (2007) “A statistical consultant programmed a computer-generated randomization code and prepared the packages of medication” [70]

Malik (2014) “We randomized the treatment allocation by simple randomization using computer generated random numbers (Excel 2010)” [79]

Rerksuppaphol (2013) “Using a computerized programme (GraphPad QuickCals), the enrolled children were randomized to the zinc or placebo group using blocks of two by a statistical consultant who was not involved in the implementation phase of the study” [72]

Turner (2000) challenge “Subjects were randomized to receive study medication” [63].

There are several inconsistencies in Nault’s assessment of randomization.

Nault gave the Farr (1987) Trial2 a “?” but the Trial1 a “+” although the texts in the Farr report are similar for both trials, compare above. It is unlikely that the randomization methods in parallel trials run by the same researchers would differ substantially.

Nault gave Turner (2000) natural trial a “?” but the challenge trial a “+” although the texts in the Turner report are also very similar for both trials, compare above. Again, it is unlikely that

the randomization methods in parallel trials run by the same researchers would differ substantially.

Similarly, why is the “research consultant prepared the randomization code” in the (Prasad 2000, 2008) trials unsatisfactory,

whereas

“Randomization by a third party” (Godfrey 1992) and

“A statistical consultant programmed a computer-generated randomization code” (Kurugöl 2006) and

“A statistical consultant programmed a computer-generated randomization code” (Kurugöl 2007) and

“randomly allocated to the sequence” (Douglas 1987), etc. are satisfactory?

Nault put a “?” for the Petrus (1998) trial. I contacted Petrus and asked about details of their methods and received the following response:

The bottles of the zinc lozenges and placebo were sent by the manufacturer and each bottle was identical except a sequential number. At registration, after qualifying for the study each patient was given a bottle of 180 lozenges. At the conclusion of the study, when the diaries were assembled, the code for the bottles was sent by the manufacturer, and the patients were placed in the zinc or placebo category. Then the results were tabulated and the statistical analysis was undertaken (Edward Petrus 24 March 2016). [8,9,10,27]

When starting a new analysis on zinc treatment for common cold, Nault should have read the previous meta-analyses on zinc lozenges and would have found that there is additional information about the Petrus (1998) trial.

Another questionable classification by Nault was to put a “+” mark for the RoB table for the Rerksuppaphol (2013) trial which *reported* highly significant baseline difference for age and height ($P = 0.0001$); see above. The goal of randomization is to minimize selection bias. When such a great imbalance is observed and reported, the bias does not disappear with a “satisfactory” description of randomization methods.

Selective reporting

Nault put a question mark “?” on nearly all trials [23, figure 3].

The Cochrane Handbook states [80]:

This domain addresses bias that arises because the reported result is selected (based on its direction, magnitude or statistical significance) from among multiple intervention effect estimates that were calculated by the trial authors.

The item is relevant, for example, in trials on pain, in which case there can be a dozen different measures for pain experience. In fact, pain is used as one example in the Cochrane Handbook [80]:

Selective reporting of a particular outcome measurement (based on the results) from among estimates for multiple measurements assessed within an outcome domain.

Examples include: ... use of multiple measurement instruments (e.g. pain scales) and only reporting data for the instrument with the most favourable result ...

There are no similar concerns about the duration of the common cold which cannot be measured in a dozen different ways. It is not clear why Nault has given a “?” to the majority of trials.

Potential for bias depends on what was found

If a trial finds a positive effect, then it is reasonable to consider whether systematic biases might explain the observed difference, or part of it. However, if there is no difference between trial groups, then the concern of bias is different. If the observed null effect is thought to be a result of bias, then the critic believes that the true unbiased effect is not null.

Weismann (1990) found no difference between the zinc lozenge and placebo groups. Nault put the “-” mark on the “Random sequence generation” item of the trial in the risk of bias table, which means “High risk of selection bias”. Thus, this indicates that the null effect is biased in Nault’s view.

However, Nault et al. do not discuss whether they believe that the unbiased estimate in Weismann’s trial indicates harm or benefit from zinc lozenges, if they consider that the observed null effect is biased.

Smith (1989) found no difference between the zinc lozenge and placebo groups.

Nault put a “-” mark on the “Incomplete outcome data” item of the trial in the risk of bias table, which means “High risk of attrition bias”.

However, Nault et al. do not discuss whether they believe that the unbiased estimate in Smith’s trial indicates harm or benefit from zinc lozenges, if they consider that the observed null effect is biased.

Turner (2001) found no difference between the nasal zinc and placebo groups.

Nault put a “?” mark on the “Blinding of participants and personnel” and “Blinding of outcome assessment” items of the trial, which means “Unclear risk of performance and detection bias”.

However, Nault et al. do not discuss whether they believe that the unbiased estimate in Turner’s (2001) trial indicates harm or benefit from zinc lozenges, if they consider that the observed null effect is biased.

Thus, it is not clear that Nault considered the actual potential for bias in the included trials.

Some notes on valid and invalid criticisms

Comments on methodological evaluation of RCTs by Meinert (1986) are thoughtful [81]:

Valid and invalid criticisms:

There is no such thing as a perfect study, only varying degrees of imperfection. The professional critic can always cite one or more of the criticisms listed in Table 26-3 without fear of contradiction. For example, he can always argue that the results of the trial should be ignored because the investigators studied the “wrong” population. Or he can challenge the choice of treatments or the way in which they were administered. And it is always possible to chide investigators because they failed to collect “important”

data—at least as viewed from the perspective of the critic. The problem is not coming up with criticisms, but in deciding whether or not they are valid. The trouble with the criticisms listed in Table 26-3 is that they are so broad and sweeping as to be beyond debate.

A criticism, to be valid, should:

- Have some basis in fact
- Be buttressed with supporting evidence
- *Make a difference in the interpretation of the results* [italics added]

All three tests should be met. *Among the three, the third is the most difficult one to satisfy.* For example, it is fairly easy to criticize a trial because of differences in the baseline composition of the treatment groups. *However, it is quite another thing to show how those differences might have accounted for the results observed.* The variability has to be sizable and must occur in connection with an important predictor of outcome to make any real differences in the results.

Table 26-3 Universal criticisms [shortened to a few examples]

- Treatment protocol not followed in all cases
- Treatments not properly administered
- Design of the study flawed (wrong design, inadequate stratification, *wrong method of randomization*)
- Execution of the trial faulty
- Results not definitive

Nault does not show how the "bias" may have accounted for the lack of observed benefit in the Weismann, Smith, and Turner trials.

Analysis of adverse effects is not appropriate

The most common adverse effects of zinc lozenges are bad taste and irritation and dryness in the mouth, and gastrointestinal discomfort.

Nault's conclusion on adverse effects of zinc treatment in the Abstract [23, p.2]:

There is probably an increase in the risk of non-serious adverse events when zinc is used for cold treatment (RR 1.34 ...); no treatment study provided information on serious adverse events.

However, there are flaws in Nault's analysis of adverse effects.

First, the variation in lozenge composition is not taken into account: uniform adverse effects should not be expected.

Second, estimating the size of the adverse effect as a RR is not meaningful when the focus is on mild adverse effects.

In his reviews, Eby pointed out that the taste problems of zinc lozenges largely depend on the composition of the lozenges:

Unlike some unhelpful zinc gluconate lozenges, zinc acetate lozenges are flavour-stable and do not become bitter regardless of time or storage conditions. Properly prepared ZIA 100 zinc acetate lozenges have no objectionable taste or aftertaste in common cold treatment. They do not seem to produce side-effects previously associated with zinc gluconate lozenges, perhaps because much less zinc acetate is required to produce identical results than zinc gluconate or any other suitable zinc compound [2, p.491].

ZG [zinc gluconate] lozenges manufactured without dextrose-based carbohydrates are bland tasting and produce a tannic acid-like mouth feel. However, when carbohydrates (excluding fructose) are used in lozenges, a slow chemical reaction occurs, which over a few weeks to a few months time results in a change in flavor of ZG from bland to noisomely bitter. Consequently, some means of preventing this reaction was needed to produce pleasant tasting lozenges containing ZG.

Two to ten moles of glycine relative to ZG prevents the adverse flavor reaction according to US patent 4,684,528 licensed to the Quigley Corporation (Doylestown, PA), the manufacturer of Cold-Eeze brand zinc gluconate–glycine (ZGG) lozenges [3, p.29].

Several trials used other food acids to flavor-mask the bitter ZG/dextrose reaction, resulting in loss of efficacy... [3, p.31].

Although pure ZG is bland and chalky in taste, it reacts with dextrose and related carbohydrates (excluding fructose) upon aging of lozenge compositions to produce noisome bitterness and compliance-related inefficacy. ZG releases large amounts of neutrally charged hydroxide species likely to cross cell membranes and causes oral irritation. Bitterness occurs in all ZG lozenges except those that either do not contain carbohydrates (excluding fructose), or that contain strong extramolar zinc binding agents, which results in something other than ZG. For these reasons, ZG is no longer believed suitable for use in zinc lozenges for treating colds. [3, p.34-35].

On the other hand, ZA [zinc acetate] allows the production of pleasant tasting, flavor stable lozenges releasing large amounts of iZn [free zinc ions] either in hard candies or

compressed tablets without flavor or stability issues. The mouth-feel produced is sufficiently like the mouth-feel of tea (slight astringency) to allow using tannic acid without added bitter agents as a placebo in clinical trials [3, p.35].

Fructose is the only carbohydrate sweetener that does not become bitter after aging for several weeks when combined with zinc gluconate [4, p.484].

Due to serious taste issues zinc gluconate was a poor choice for treating colds. Zinc gluconate forms extremely bitter complexes with all sweet carbohydrates except fructose... The overriding source of failure was requirement by pharmaceutical marketing companies for pleasant tasting, candy-like, non-metallic, non-astringent and non-drying zinc lozenges [4, p.488].

Given this impact of zinc lozenge composition on taste, it is evident that the composition should be considered when considering non-severe adverse effects.

Furthermore, the pertinent question is the frequency and type of adverse effects from the lozenge compositions that worked (Figures 2 and 3), and not the frequency and type of adverse effects from the zinc lozenges that did not work, such as lozenges containing citric acid, tartaric acid, mannitol/sorbitol, orotate, etc.

In my RCT, I also pointed out that

the rapid dissolution of lozenges may have exacerbated taste and other adverse effects. If 80 mg/day of zinc is dissolved in mouth over 0.7 hours per day, the temporary zinc ion concentrations in the oropharyngeal region are several times higher compared with the same zinc dose being dissolved over some 3 hours per day [66].

It is also evident that the dosage influences, for example, gastrointestinal discomfort, so the occurrence of adverse effects should be considered as a function of dosage.

Finally, regarding minor adverse effects such as taste, it is not reasonable to compare zinc lozenges with placebo lozenges, when the goal in an RCT is to formulate a placebo that tastes the same as the zinc lozenge. If the placebo is perfect, the placebo lozenge and the zinc lozenge cannot be distinguished by taste or other effects unrelated to the common cold. However, this means that both the placebo and the zinc lozenges can taste so terrible that no patient wants to continue the intervention, even though the adverse effects of zinc lozenges would not differ from the placebo lozenges when measured as a RR. Thus, the lack of difference between an ideal placebo and zinc lozenge does not indicate lack of adverse effects of the particular zinc lozenges.

Because of these issues, Nault's calculation of a single estimate for adverse effect such as RR = 1.34 "when zinc is used for cold treatment" [23, p.2] is scientifically unsound. When the adverse effects are minor and short-lasting, such that they disappear with the termination of zinc lozenge administration, the RR is not a reasonable measure for the adverse effects.

Nault writes about the analysis of adverse effects of zinc treatments as follows:

We pooled 16 treatment studies (Belongia 2001; Caesar 2012; Eby 1984; Eby 2006; Godfrey 1992; Hemilä 2020; Hirt 2000; Macknin 1998; Mossad 1996; Mossad 2003; Petrus 1998; Prasad 2000; Prasad 2008; Turner 2000 challenge; Turner 2000 natural; Weismann 1990). There is probably an increase in the risk of experiencing non-serious

adverse events for those taking zinc compared with those taking placebo (RR 1.34, 95% CI 1.15 to 1.55; $I^2 = 44\%$; 16 studies, 2084 participants; moderate-certainty evidence; Analysis 11.1). [23, p.22]

Belongia (2001) administered 0.044 mg/day zinc.

Eby (1984) administered 207 mg/day zinc, which is 4700 times Belongia's dose.

Godfrey (1992) administered 190 mg/day zinc, which is 4300 times Belongia's dose.

There is no basis to consider that trials with over a 4000-fold difference in zinc dosage are "similar enough for pooling to make sense".

Caesar (2012) administered 20 mg/day zinc as powder, while powder is different from nasal zinc and zinc lozenges, and there is no basis to assume the same adverse effects.

Furthermore, there are calculation errors in the doses of Mossad (1996) and Prasad (2000) trials, see section "Flaws in data extraction". In Analysis 11.4. (Adverse event by dose of zinc), Nault classifies these trials in the "high dose" >85 mg/day subgroup, whereas the correct doses are less than 85 mg/day and thus the trials should be in the "low dose" <85 mg/day subgroup.

As noted above, there is also no basis to assume that the adverse effects of zinc lozenges (Eby 1984; Godfrey 1992; Hemilä 2020; Macknin 1998; Mossad 1996; Petrus 1998; Prasad 2000; Prasad 2008; Turner 2000; Weismann 1990) and nasal zinc (Belongia 2001; Hirt 2000; Mossad 2003) are similar enough to pool them together.

In fact, Nault writes in the Methods section that they did not pool oral and intranasal zinc:

Because the likely mechanisms and potential adverse effects of oral and intranasal zinc differ, we analysed trials of oral zinc (including tablets, capsules, syrups, or lozenges) separately from trials of intranasal zinc (including sprays or gels).

However, in Nault's Analysis 11.1 this description of methods was not followed. Given that there are 10 authors in the Cochrane review [23] and all are expected to read and accept the text, it is concerning that not one of them wondered whether the reported methods and the actual methods were consistent.

The most relevant measure for assessing mild adverse effects of zinc lozenges seems to be the proportion of patients who do not experience discomforts which are too annoying, and the proportion who do not discontinue the treatment. With this reasoning, I assembled relevant data about the zinc lozenge groups of the more important trials (Table 2).

Table 2. Adverse effects of zinc lozenges.

Trial / Adverse effects	Patients with	Patients without	Proportion without the adverse effect
Godfrey (1992)			
Zinc gluconate, N = 35			
Any adverse effects	20	15	43%
Gastrointestinal discomfort	13	22	63%
Mouth irritation	12	23	66%
Dizziness	3	32	91%
Mossad (1996)			
Zinc gluconate, N = 49			
Any adverse effects	44	5	10%
Nausea	10	39	80%
Constipation	1	48	98%
Mouth irritation	12	37	76%
Mouth dryness	6	43	88%
Bad taste	39	10	20%
Prasad (2000)			
Zinc acetate, N = 25			
Nausea	0	25	100%
Constipation	6	19	76%
Mouth irritation	10	15	60%
Mouth dryness	18	7	28%
Bad taste	13	12	48%
Prasad (2008)			
Zinc acetate, N = 25			
Nausea	3	22	88%
Constipation	2	23	92%
Mouth irritation	1	24	96%
Mouth dryness	13	12	48%
Bad taste	15	10	40%
Sweet taste	11	14	56%
Bitter taste	8	17	68%
Sour taste	7	18	72%
Hemilä (2020)			
Zinc acetate, N = 46			
Any adverse effects	29	17	37%
Stomach ache	12	34	74%
Taste problems	24	22	48%

The table shows the reported adverse effects in the zinc groups of the trials.

Godfrey (1992) [36] reported that 43% of the zinc lozenge participants did not report any adverse effects. In the zinc lozenge group, 1 withdrew for sports injury, 1 for influenza, 1 for bacterial infection, and 1 because of doubting efficacy: these 4 are not withdrawals because of adverse effects. In addition, in the zinc lozenge group, 1 withdrew for nausea and 3 failed to appear at a follow-up. The latter 4 patients may be related to adverse effect of zinc lozenges, which gives 2% (1/43) as the minimum percentage (though nausea may also be caused by the virus), and 9% (4/43) as the maximum percentage who withdrew because of adverse effects.

Mossad (1996) [45] reported that 10% of the 49 zinc lozenge patients had no adverse effects. Mossad wrote: “*One patient in the zinc group withdrew from the study on the first day because she could not tolerate the lozenges.*” However, Mossad continued: “*All other patients, as directly observed by the study nurse, indicated that they had good tolerance of the first lozenge.*” Furthermore, “*two zinc recipients dropped out after 7 to 16 days*” but there is no information on the reasons. Thus, 2% withdrew because of not tolerating the zinc lozenge, while 94% continued to the end (not making guesses for the 2 dropouts at the later stage).

Prasad (2000) [39] and Prasad (2008) [40] did not publish how many participants reported no adverse effects. In both trials, issues with bad taste were reported by about half the participants. However, none of the participants in the zinc groups (50 = 25 + 25 in the zinc groups of the 2 trials) withdrew from the trial, indicating that the adverse effects were quite mild in the opinion of the patients. In the 2000 trial, “two participants in the placebo group dropped out on day 2” but that is not explained as an adverse effect of the zinc lozenges.

Hemilä (2020) [66] found that 37% (95% CI: 23% to 53%) of zinc lozenge participants did not complain of any adverse effects.

In summary, there is great variation in whether, and how, different patients experience discomfort from the tested zinc lozenges. While a substantial proportion of patients have not experienced adverse effects, a few have discontinued trials because of them.

All the reported adverse effects in the zinc lozenge trials were minor inconveniences. Thus, if a patient starts testing whether zinc lozenges are useful for his or her current common cold, the patient suffering from acute adverse effects such as bad taste can simply stop taking the lozenges. Such an approach would not be different from the ordinary use of over-the-counter medicines. For example, if a patient takes a painkiller for headache, but gets stomach ache as an adverse effect, the patient can discontinue the medication any time. A stomach ache for an individual patient does not prevent other people from using painkillers for their headaches.

The proportion of patients who don’t get adverse effects from zinc lozenges (Table 1) appears a much more useful approach to analyze the occurrence of minor adverse effects from zinc lozenges than the “*the risk of non-serious adverse events when zinc is used for cold treatment (RR 1.34 ...)*” reported by Nault [23, p.2].

In the Plain Language Summary, Nault writes [23, p.3]:

Studies administering intranasal zinc did not report any cases of anosmia (loss of sense of smell)

However, analysis of adverse effects of zinc should not be limited to the small RCTs included in the meta-analysis estimating the treatment efficacy. There are relevant data outside of the trials included by Nault.

Long-lasting anosmia is a much more concerning adverse effect than short-lasting constipation, nausea or bad taste. However, anosmia is such an uncommon problem that it is not necessarily captured by small RCTs, yet there are other data that raise concern about nasal zinc administration [41-44].

Nevertheless, it seems evident that an unknown proportion of the anosmia cases are caused by the viruses that cause the common cold, so that anosmia after the nasal zinc treatment is not necessarily caused by the zinc treatment itself. It has been known over centuries that the common cold can cause anosmia. François Boissier de Sauvages (1772) classified anosmia to several types with Type 1 being “anosmia catarrhalis” which meant “It is what accompanies the common cold, and when it is stubborn, it remains even after it is cured” [82]. Recent studies have found that in patients with anosmia, rhinoviruses, old coronaviruses, and Epstein-Barr virus were detected [83,84]. In an experimental study, inoculation with the old coronavirus 229E caused impaired olfaction [85]. The capacity of viruses to cause anosmia has been even more dramatic with COVID-19 [86,87]. The case reports proposing that nasal zinc administration caused anosmia [42,43] are methodologically poor, with no convincing arguments that it was zinc and not the virus that caused anosmia.

Davidson and Smith (2010) used the “Bradford Hill criteria” to argue that it was zinc that caused anosmia [44]. Their reasoning is not sound, however. The “Hill criteria” do not allow drawing cause-effect conclusions [88]. Rothman wrote that “we can hardly criticize Hill for originating the checklist, because he asked to be counted among the critics of a checklist approach to inference. He studiously avoided the word ‘criteria’ in his talk, and he cautioned against using his ‘viewpoints’ as if they were criteria, claiming that none of them was a *sine qua non* for causal inference” [89].

Davidson and Smith claimed that “the strength of the association between the use of zinc nasal spray and rapid-onset anosmia is strong” [44]. However, this was not based on any kind of estimation of the RR for a patient to get anosmia after the common cold treated with nasal zinc vs. after the common cold *not* treated with nasal zinc administration.

Nevertheless, as noted above, estimation of efficacy of nasal zinc administration to treat colds is not relevant until there is a better understanding whether and which kinds of nasal zinc administration cause and do not cause anosmia, or whether the cases of anosmia are caused by the viruses that are being treated.

Other sources for relevant information about potential severe adverse effects of high doses of zinc are trials with high doses of zinc for other diseases, and treatment of patients with the Wilson’s disease.

For certain patients, zinc has been administered in high doses, 100 to 150 mg/day of zinc, for therapeutic purposes for months or years without serious adverse effects [90-99].

Finally, starting from adolescence, 150 mg/day of zinc is currently one of the standard treatments for Wilson’s disease, which usually means taking such doses for the rest of one’s life [100-104]. In the treatment of Wilson’s disease, zinc has had an excellent safety profile, although it has caused gastric irritation in about 10% of the patients [102].

Because of these data, it seems highly unlikely that 80–92 mg/day of elemental zinc used in the zinc lozenge trials [37,39,40,45] for 1-2 weeks can lead to long-term adverse effects. In this respect, the analysis of zinc safety by Nault is not informative.

PICO criteria were not considered in the Cochrane review (2024)

Finding specific answers requires that specific questions are posed.

The Cochrane Library instructs readers to look at **PICO** [105]:

PICO stands for four different potential components of a health question used in Cochrane Review research:

Patient, Population or Problem

What are the characteristics of the patient or population (demographics, risk factors, pre-existing conditions, etc)?

What is the condition or disease of interest?

Intervention

What is the intervention under consideration for this patient or population?

Comparison

What is the alternative to the intervention (e.g. placebo, different drug, surgery)?

Outcome

What are the included outcomes (e.g. quality of life, change in clinical status, morbidity, adverse effects, complications)?

These components give you the specific who, what, when, where and how, of an evidence-based health-care research question.

The PICO model is widely used and taught in evidence-based health care as a strategy for defining review criteria, formulating questions and search strategies, and for characterizing included studies or meta-analyses.

The Cochrane Handbook also contains instructions on using PICO. Chapter 2.3 [105]:

The PICO for each synthesis (also planned at the protocol stage) defines the question that each specific synthesis aims to answer, determining how the synthesis will be structured, specifying planned comparisons (including intervention and comparator groups, any grouping of outcome and population subgroups).

The PICO of the included studies (determined at the review stage) is what was actually investigated in the included studies.

Let us consider an analogy. If a researcher is interested in the effect of antibiotics on mortality caused by infections, and combines all antibiotics into a single broad category of ‘antibiotics’, and pools all ‘antibiotic trials’ with different types of patients together, anyone with a basic background in clinical microbiology would consider such a project silly. Different antibiotics kill different bacteria, there is geographic and social group variation in the occurrence of pathogenic bacteria, the usage of antibiotics generates resistant strains, there are many types of patients, and so on. The biology of antibiotics is very complex. It is obvious that a single universal estimate for the “antibiotic effect on mortality” over all patients and all antibiotics is meaningless.

A similar problem arises in Nault’s Cochrane review. As shown in Figures 2 and 3 above, with the data collected and accepted by Nault, it is feasible to draw a firm and specific answer that

“there is strong evidence that properly composed zinc acetate and zinc gluconate lozenges can substantially shorten common colds in adults with a 37% decrease in the duration of colds as the best estimate currently”. This analysis limits **P** to adults, and **I** to zinc lozenges.

In contrast, Nault’s Analysis 9.1 covers **P** over all ages, and **I** pools over both zinc lozenges and nasal zinc administration, even though there is a 4300-fold variation in the zinc dosage in the trials included in Nault’s Analysis 9.1. Nault’s very broad PICO does not lead to any specific answer since there is no specific question.

The PICO type of reasoning also means that a reviewer should properly describe the contexts of each trial.

In their report on a trial with 6-11 month old children in India, Malik (2014) [79] wrote that: “*We hypothesized that zinc supplementation for 2 weeks will reduce the incidence of ARIs in subsequent months*”.

They described the intervention:

The field investigator administered the first dose of the intervention at the time of recruitment and advised the mother to give 5 mL of syrup (using standard 5 mL plastic spoon) daily to the infant for the remaining 13 days. Subsequently visits were made on the 7th and the 14th day to ensure compliance

and then they described the follow-up:

Follow-up for ARIs began at the 15th day postintervention. Each child was followed up fortnightly (± 3) days and the follow-up continued till 5 months after completion of zinc/placebo supplementation. At each follow-up, mother/caregiver was asked about history of ARIs during the previous 15 days.

The essential part of PICO type of reasoning in this case is that: **I** there is a 2-week intervention and **O** the follow-up for the outcome starts after the intervention is ended from week 3 to month 5. Some treatments such as vaccination and surgery cause long-lasting effects and therefore long follow-ups are appropriate. However, it is not obvious that zinc supplementation has similar long-lasting effects, though Malik may formulate such a hypothesis.

Nault [23, p.18-19] describes the Malik (2014) trial [79] as follows:

Malik 2014 found a 1% increase in the number of URTIs (incidence rate ratio (IRR) 1.01, 95% CI 0.89 to 1.14) when the zinc group was compared to control.

Malik 2014 reported that, on average, their zinc group experienced 11.4 (6.6) days with ARI compared with the placebo group’s average of 14.7 (8.0) days.

In neither case does Nault describe that this trial was testing a hypothesis that a short zinc administration (**I**) might cause long-lasting effects on the occurrence of ARI (**O**) in the young children after the intervention ends. Thus, if a reader looks at the findings in the Malik (2014) trial according to Nault – without reading the Malik (2014) report – the reader assumes that the above outcomes are recorded during the zinc treatment.

In the section “*Overall completeness and applicability of evidence*”, Nault writes that:

The majority of the trials were conducted in adults (22/34). This may impact generalisability in all populations. The number of participants in the trials was small (12 of 34 studies included ≥ 200 participants), which may limit precision, even when metaanalysed [23, p.27].

There is no basis to assume that a single estimate of effect applies for all different zinc treatments and for all different patients. Had Nault properly analyzed effects of zinc lozenges on common colds of adults, then the analysis could have been generalized to “zinc lozenges” as the **I** and “adults” as the **P** (Figure 2).

Furthermore, a small number of participants can lead to false negative findings, but small number of participants is not a reasonable cause for false positive findings. In Figure 2, the confidence interval is narrow (95% CI: 27-46%) indicating good precision for the 37% estimate of effect. When precision is good, then the number of participants cannot be too small.

In the section “*Agreements and disagreements with other studies or reviews*”, Nault writes:

Several meta-analyses and reviews have been conducted in this area...

This current review expands on these existing reviews by including all methods of administration and formulations of zinc for prevention or treatment of colds in adults and children [23, p.27].

As described above, it is not reasonable to assume that zinc lozenges and nasal zinc, and 0.044 mg/day and 190 mg/day are “similar enough”. It is also not reasonable to assume that effects are identical in adults and children. There can be physiological differences or differences in the experimental conditions such that children may have greater tendency to cheat. The PICO reasoning is useful, but was not followed by Nault.

A PICO kind of brief summary of the main findings from the zinc lozenge trials:

Compared with a placebo group (**C**),
in adults (**P**) zinc acetate and zinc gluconate lozenges (**I**) shorten the duration of common colds (**O**) by 37%, whereas
in children (**P**) there is no evidence so far that zinc acetate and zinc gluconate lozenges (**I**) shorten the duration of common colds (**O**)

These statements are based on Figures 2 and 3.

Potential explanations for the negative results in the Hemilä (2020) trial were ignored

In 2020, I published an RCT on zinc acetate lozenges for treating the common cold. The findings were negative [66]. However, there are a few plausible explanations for the negative findings, but they are not discussed by Nault. The relevant sections from the Discussion are copied here.

The unexpected null finding suggests that uncertainty in the efficacy of commercially available zinc lozenges and inappropriate understanding of proper instructions for their use remains. In half of the positive trials, the lozenges weighed about 4 g, whereas our lozenge weighed only 0.9 g (table 4 [66]). In five previous trials, the dissolving time of the lozenge in the mouth was 15–30 min, and the cumulative time the participant had a lozenge dissolving in mouth was from 2.3 to 3.4 hours per day. In our study, the lozenges dissolved in mouth in just 8 min and the cumulative time the participant had a lozenge dissolving in the mouth was only 0.7 hours per day. Two of the positive trials did not report how long their lozenge dissolved in the mouth; however, their lozenges weighed over 4 g [36,45], and it seems evident that they dissolved much more slowly than our 0.9 g lozenges. In addition, in one of the two trials [36], participants used 8.1 lozenges daily, which also increases the cumulative time of dissolving the lozenge compared with the average of 5.1 lozenges in our study.

Although we had recognised that the lozenges in our study were small and dissolved quite rapidly, we did not anticipate that the small size might render these lozenges inactive. Instead, we assumed that the particularly rapid initiation of treatment in our study, with half of the patients starting treatment within 4 hours after the start of common cold symptoms, would provide compensation even if the small size of the lozenge might not be ideal in terms of efficacy. Furthermore, the rapid dissolution of lozenges may have exacerbated taste and other adverse effects. If 80 mg/day of zinc is dissolved in mouth over 0.7 hours per day, the temporary zinc ion concentrations in the oropharyngeal region are several times higher compared with the same zinc dose being dissolved over some 3 hours per day. Evidently, further trials on zinc lozenges should compare the effectiveness between lozenges with various dissolving times.

We considered that the 5-day treatment should be sufficient to demonstrate an effect of zinc acetate lozenges, since in a meta-analysis of three trials with zinc acetate lozenges, a significant benefit of zinc lozenges was seen within 5 days of treatment [10]. We also assumed that the rapid initiation of zinc lozenges might lead to effects that extend beyond the active treatment period. Nevertheless, the 5-day treatment might have been too short. We found a substantial decrease in the rate of recovery in the zinc participants after the 5-day treatment ended which could be caused by the rebound effect so that the discontinuation of the zinc lozenge treatment had a physiological effect in the harmful direction. Further research is needed to confirm this and it seems evident that further trials on zinc lozenges should not be limited to 5 days of treatment. Some previous studies have administered zinc lozenges for up to 2 weeks [45,37].

In our study protocol, we calculated that six lozenges containing 13 mg zinc lead to 78 mg/day of elemental zinc, which is quite consistent with four previous studies in which zinc lozenges were effective [7,8,45,37,39,40]. However, we did not take into account that the actual lozenge usages will be lower than planned. On average zinc participants used 65 mg/day of zinc. Although we do not assume that the dose-response between

zinc lozenges and their efficacy is such steep that the difference between 65 mg/day and 80–92 mg/day of zinc would explain the inefficacy of our lozenge, further research should examine whether our somewhat low dose is a further factor that led to the negative findings. Apparently, further studies should first use actual doses that are over 92 mg/day and the search for minimal effective dose per day should be carried out only after confirming that a particular formulation is effective.

Although the trial did not find a reduction in common cold duration, the abrupt termination of zinc lozenge administration caused a rebound effect so that after the zinc lozenge administration was stopped, the participants in the zinc group recovered significantly less rapidly over a few days when compared with the placebo group. Although such a finding does not support the particular lozenge and administration schedule for the treatment of colds, the rebound effect is consistent with the pharmacological effect of zinc lozenges influencing common cold duration. The finding was described in the Results section as follows [66].

Among the zinc participants who did not have taste or other adverse effects, there were two consecutive days at the end of the 5-day treatment when no participant recovered from the common cold, suggesting that termination of treatment might have reduced the rate of recovery temporarily (figure 2B). This phenomenon is seen among all the zinc participants as a bulge after the end of the 5-day zinc treatment (figure 2A). On the fourth day, there were 36 participants still sick in the zinc lozenge group and 32 participants in the placebo group (figure 2). Of the participants still sick on the fourth day, 28% (10/36) of the zinc participants recovered by the seventh day, whereas 66% (21/32) of the placebo participants recovered by the seventh day ($p = 0.003$).

Thus, the Hemilä (2020) trial should not be interpreted as evidence against all types of zinc lozenges. It is evidence only about the specific zinc lozenge that was tested and only for 5-day treatment.

Another case of the rebound effect, unrelated to zinc lozenges, occurred in 2 RCTs with 4-day intravenous vitamin C administration (16 g/day for a 80 kg patient) to sepsis patients [106], and critically ill COVID-19 patients [107]. In both RCTs, the abrupt termination of vitamin C administration caused statistically significant increases in mortality soon after the termination of vitamin C. Thus, the rebound effect has also been observed in other contexts. Although the rebound effect is consistent with a physiological effect, it does not justify the tested zinc lozenge and protocol, but rather encourages further research.

Misleading Background section

In the Background section, Nault writes:

Whilst many people believe that zinc may be helpful in preventing or treating colds, there is currently no established intervention to prevent colds or to shorten their duration.

This statement ignores our Cochrane review on vitamin C and the common cold [29-32]. We showed that regular vitamin C supplementation of ≥ 0.2 g/day shortened the duration of colds separately in adults by 7.7% ($P = 0.0002$) and in children by 14% ($P = 0.00005$) [32]. We also calculated that in 5 trials with participants under heavy short-term physical stress, vitamin C reduced the incidence of colds by $RR = 0.52$ ($P = 0.000001$).

In our 2023 meta-analysis on the effects of vitamin C on the severity of common cold symptoms, we restricted to 15 comparisons in which ≥ 1 g/day vitamin C was administered to participants initially in good health, and when a common cold occurred, the severity was decreased on average by 15% ($P = 0.000002$) in the vitamin C groups [47]. Thus, there is very strong evidence that in certain contexts vitamin C can prevent colds and reduce their duration and severity.

Bias against using vitamin C to prevent and treat the common cold has been demonstrated in several papers [24,108-128].

Nault also ignores 4 placebo-controlled RCTs on nasal iota-carrageenan [129-132] and 2 meta-analyses based on those RCTs [133,134]. In an Individual Patient Data (IPD) meta-analysis of 2 trials in which iota-carrageenan was administered nasally 3 times per day for 7 days for patients with the common cold [129,130], we calculated that nasal carrageenan increased the recovery rate from all colds by 54% (95% CI: 15-105%; $P = 0.003$) [133]. The increase in the recovery rate was 139% for coronavirus infections, 119% for influenza A infections, and 70% for rhinovirus infections.

In a Quantile Treatment Effect analysis of the nasal carrageenan trials, there was no indication of a meaningful benefit for patients who had colds shorter than one week; however, for patients who had colds lasting two weeks or more, carrageenan shortened colds by up to 5–7 days [14,133]. Another IPD meta-analysis also concluded that there was evidence that carrageenan was effective [134]. Furthermore, in addition to the 2 carrageenan trials for which IPD was available, 2 further RCTs reported that nasal carrageenan was beneficial for common cold patients [131,132].

Thus, independent of the zinc lozenge trials (Figures 2 and 3), there is strong evidence from RCTs that vitamin C and nasal iota-carrageenan can be beneficial for colds.

Practical implications and guidance for further research

Implications for practice

This Cochrane review found varied evidence to support the effectiveness of zinc in the prevention or treatment of the common cold. Zinc supplementation may provide some limited benefits for people with the common cold. On the basis of this review, the current evidence is insufficient to provide firm conclusions or recommend zinc supplementation for the prevention or treatment of the common cold [23, p.28].

“Zinc supplementation may provide some limited benefits for people with the common cold... zinc supplementation...”

As described above, zinc lozenges and nasal zinc *are not* forms of dietary supplementation of zinc.

As to the RCT results in the trials on zinc lozenges, the statement *“may provide some limited benefit”* is an understatement, see Figures 2 and 3.

The statement “some limited benefits” is obscure. If a reduction in the duration of colds by the Cochrane estimate of 2.37-days [23] is too limited to be of practical relevance, how large an effect would Nault require before viewing the effect as relevant for ordinary common cold patients.? In comparison, painkillers are often used to help common cold symptoms, but there is no evidence that they shorten colds at all.

In any case, with a more statistically-robust analysis (Figures 2 and 3), Nault could have concluded that “on the basis of published trials on zinc acetate and zinc gluconate lozenges, they can shorten common colds in adults on average by 37%”. In doing so, the authors would leave it to the reader to decide whether the effect is large enough to justify the reader to test zinc lozenges himself or herself.

Although the zinc lozenge trials have implications for practice, the readers should be informed of the problems of the lozenges on the market [4,67], and should be guided to search for formulations that are expected to be effective.

See also the section *“PICO criteria were not considered”*

If a researcher has carefully reviewed a topic, usually it is constructive to suggest directions for future research. Nault concludes:

Implications for research

... Future researchers should note the need for standardised methods when providing zinc supplementation for the prevention or treatment of the common cold. More research is needed to determine the exact zinc type, dose, and duration of supplementation appropriate for the prevention or treatment of the common cold. Future directions for research might be to consider exploring the subjective experience or quality of life of participants while taking zinc, increasing the diversity of characteristics in the participants recruited (varied race/ethnicity, age, gender, health status), and further examining factors that may interfere with the bioavailability of zinc [23, p.29]

This instruction is not particularly helpful for further research.

“*Standardized methods*” is obscure without further definition.

“... *to determine the exact zinc type, dose, and duration of supplementation appropriate for the prevention or treatment of the common cold*”

What type of zinc salt should have priority? What is a reasonable dose? Ordinary tablets or zinc lozenges or nasal zinc? Given that Nault has read the reports on zinc trials, questions such as these should be commented on.

To my knowledge there is no evidence indicating that ordinary zinc tablets that are intended to be swallowed whole have effects on colds in the Western adult population. Nault also does not provide any evidence for benefits of dietary zinc supplementation. Nasal zinc administration should not be a high priority until the concerns about anosmia have been resolved; see above.

There is strong evidence that properly composed zinc lozenges can reduce common cold duration as shown in Figures 2 and 3 and in references [1-14] and therefore further research on zinc lozenges should have a high priority.

My 2011 and 2017 meta-analyses indicated that there was much stronger evidence for the effects of zinc acetate lozenges when compared with zinc gluconate lozenges [7,8], which is also shown in Figure 3. Therefore, the highest priority should be to further examine zinc acetate lozenges. There does not seem to be any particular benefit from using zinc gluconate lozenges.

My 2017 dose-response analysis did not find any difference in the effects of 5 trials using elemental zinc doses from 80 to 92 mg/day compared with 2 trials that used substantially higher doses of zinc, 192 and 207 mg/day [8]. However, the Turner (2000) trial found no benefit from 80 mg/day zinc (instructed dose, but actual dose was not reported) as zinc gluconate lozenges [63], and my own RCT with 65 mg/day zinc (actual used dose) as zinc acetate lozenges did not find any benefit, though my trial demonstrated the rebound effect when the 5-day zinc dosage was terminated [66]. On this basis, it seems obvious that 200 mg/day elemental zinc is not needed, but 80 mg/day may be too low to lead to consistent benefits. Therefore, a dosage of around 120 mg/day might be reasonable in further research when trying to repeat the previous positive findings. Thereafter the lowest effective doses and optimal lozenge compositions could be searched for.

A further aspect of the zinc lozenges is the time taken to dissolve in the mouth, which has been considered by Eby [4] and Hemilä [66].

In 2008, Eby wrote about implications for research on zinc lozenges [135]:

Future studies should focus on plain zinc acetate lozenges that are chemically identical to the lozenges reported to be effective by Petrus et al. [37] in 1998, by Prasad et al. [39] in 2000, and in the upcoming report by Prasad [40]. Such lozenges have been previously described [5] and have been highly successful in treating colds both in clinical trials and in the general population. Although billions of dollars have been spent on zinc lozenges for treatment of colds, money spent on zinc lozenges containing amino, citric, or ascorbic acids may have been wasted.

Flaws in data extraction

I did not systematically check data extraction for the Nault meta-analysis, but happened to note some substantial errors.

Nault writes about the **Turner (2001)** [75] trial:

“Zinc gluconate 1200 mg/day nasal gel” [23, p.142]

However, Turner (2001) wrote:

“Study medication... The active preparation (Zicam) consisted of 33 mM zinc gluconate... Study medications were administered as a single nasal spray of 120 µL per nostril... 5 times each day.”

$120 \mu\text{L} \times 2 \text{ nostrils} \times 5 \text{ times each day} = 1200 \mu\text{L}$.

Thus, it seems that Nault confused between mg/day and µL.

The actual dose is:

$0.033 \text{ mol/L} \times 0.00012 \text{ L} \times 2 \text{ nostrils} \times 5 \text{ times each day} \times 455.7 \text{ g/mol} = 0.0180 \text{ g} = 18 \text{ mg}$ zinc gluconate per day (2.59 mg/day elemental zinc). Nault’s Cochrane review [23] has 10 authors and it is concerning that not one of them read the manuscript carefully enough to wonder whether it is possible to administer 1.2 grams of zinc gluconate nasally per day.

Nault writes about the **Hirt (2000)** [33] trial:

“Zinc gluconate 960 mg/d nasal gel” [23, p.70]

but on the same page:

“Dose per day (elemental zinc in mg): unclear” [23, p.70]

$120 \mu\text{L} \times 2 \text{ nostrils} \times 4 \text{ times each day} = 960 \mu\text{L}$.

Thus, Nault confused also here between mg/day and µL.

Reporting of the zinc dose in Hirt (2000) [33] was not clear, giving justification to the second statement “unclear”.

However, in table 2, Characteristics of interventions, Nault gives a third zinc dose in the Hirt (2000) trial:

33 mmol concentration/spray 1 × spray per nostril 4 × per day (8 total doses per day) [leading to] “Approximate zinc dose per day” of 2.1 mg/d [23, p.191].

Thus, Nault gives 3 different zinc doses for the Hirt (2000) trial:

1) 960 mg/d, 2) unclear, and 3) 2.1 mg/d.

In the calculation of the 2.1 mg/d, Nault assumed “33 mmol concentration/spray” but Hirt did not report such a zinc concentration of their gel [33]. Nevertheless, the 2.1 mg/day does have indirect justification from the Hirt (2000) report [33, p.778]:

Recently, a new approach to zinc therapy – an over-the-counter nasal gel formulation (Zicam) – was the subject of a preliminary study (C.B. Hensley, PhD, and R. Davidson, PhD, unpublished data, 1999). That study demonstrated that the direct application of the nasal gel containing 33 mmol/L of ionic zinc within 24 hours of the onset of common

cold symptoms significantly shortened the duration of those symptoms. The researchers hypothesized that the delivery of ionic zinc directly to the site of infection should be more effective than oral delivery.

The goal of our study was to attempt to reproduce those results and independently assess the effect of zinc nasal gel on the duration of common cold symptoms.

Thus Hirt did not state in their methods that they used 33 mmol/L zinc gel, but the introduction suggests so. The methods section of Hirt describes 120 µL four times per day for both nostrils, which would lead to 2.07 mg of elemental zinc, if we assume that the concentration was 33 mmol/L:

$0.033 \text{ mol/L} \times 0.00012 \text{ L} \times 2 \text{ nostrils} \times 4 \text{ times each day} \times 65.4 \text{ g/mol} = 2.07 \text{ mg/day}$
elemental zinc

I did not check through all trials included by Nault, but these below are selected further examples of data extraction and calculation errors, in addition to the two trials described above.

Hemilä (2020)

Nault writes [23, p.67]:

“Frequency of dose: 6/d... Dose per day (elemental zinc in mg): 78 mg/d”

However, Hemilä (2020) reported:

“The zinc lozenge was a commercially available zinc acetate lozenge with 13 mg elemental zinc per lozenge” [66, p.3]

“Over the period from the second to the fifth days, the zinc participants used on average 5.05 lozenges per day” [66, p. 4]

This gives the correct dose of daily elemental zinc as:

$13 \text{ mg} * 5.05 = 65.6 \text{ mg/d}$

Mossad (1996)

Nault writes [23, p.98]:

“Frequency of dose: 1 lozenge every 2 hours while awake.

Dose per day (elemental zinc in mg): 13.3 mg* (max) 12 oz/day = 159.6 mg/d”

However, Mossad (1996) reported:

“... lozenges that weighed 4.4 g and contained 13.3 mg of zinc.” [45, p.82]

“the zinc group took an average of 6 ± 2 lozenges per day (median, 5 lozenges per day)” [45, p. 84]

This gives the correct dose of daily elemental zinc as:

$13.3 \text{ mg} * 6 = 80 \text{ mg/d}$

Thus, the correct dose is half of that calculated by Nault.

This error has further consequences in Nault’s analysis.

In Analysis 11.4. (Adverse events), Nault classifies the Mossad (1996) trial in the “high dose” >85 mg/day subgroup, whereas the correct dose is <85 mg/day and thus the trial should be in the “low dose” <85 mg/day subgroup.

Prasad (2000)

Nault writes [23, p.113]:

“Dose per day (elemental zinc in mg): $12.8 \text{ mg} \times 8 = 102.4 \text{ mg}$ (estimated number of lozenges per day)”

However, Prasad (2000) reported:

“Each lozenge contained 12.8 mg of zinc.” [39, p.246]

“The average number of lozenges taken daily was 6.2 in the zinc group” [39, p.249]

This gives the correct dose of daily elemental zinc as:

$$12.8 \text{ mg} * 6.2 = 79 \text{ mg/d}$$

This error has further consequences in Nault’s analysis.

In Analysis 9.3. (Treatment effects), Nault classifies the Prasad (2000) trial in the “high dose” >85 mg/day subgroup, whereas the correct dose is <85 mg/day and thus the trial should be in the “low dose” <85 mg/day subgroup.

In Analysis 11.4. (Adverse events), Nault classifies the Prasad (2000) trial in the “high dose” >85 mg/day subgroup, whereas the correct dose is <85 mg/day and thus the trial should be in the “low dose” <85 mg/day subgroup.

Prasad (2008)

Nault writes [23, p.119]:

“Dose per day (elemental zinc in mg): $13.3 \text{ mg} * 8 = 106.4 \text{ mg/d}$ ”

However, Prasad (2008) reported:

“The active lozenges contained 13.3 mg of zinc” [40, p.796]

“The average number of lozenges taken daily was 6.9 in the zinc group” [40, p.799]

This gives the correct dose of daily elemental zinc as:

$$13.3 \text{ mg} * 6.9 = 92 \text{ mg/d}$$

Macknin (1998) trial with children [38]

In Analysis 9.1, Nault states that the mean duration of colds was 8.7 days (**SD 8.5 days**) in the zinc lozenge group, and 8.7 days (**SD 2.8 days**) in the placebo group; see Figure 1 of this document.

However, in the Characteristics of Included Studies, Nault [23, p.85] writes:

Notes: duration was only reported as median time + CI, so while CI could be converted to SD, the median could not. ‘The median time to resolution of all cold symptoms was 9.0 days (95% CI, 8-9 days) in the placebo group and 9.0 days (95% CI, 7-10 days) in the zinc group (P=.71; figure 2).’ They also reported the number whose symptoms resolved over the course of the 21 days vs those who did not. That is reported here.

There is no description where the SD 8.5 and 2.8 days of Analysis 9.1 come from.

The distribution of recovery in the zinc lozenge and placebo groups is closely overlapping and thus there cannot be a 3-fold difference in the SD values between the two trial groups, see Figure 9. Measuring the curves to reach the IPD, imputing 18 days to the censored observations at the right-hand side, gives the mean duration 9.2 days (SD 4.6 days) in the zinc lozenge group, and 9.5 days (SD 4.6 days) in the placebo group. These SD values are quite different from the SD values published by Nault in Analysis 9.1.

Figure 2.—Time to resolution of all cold symptoms among students treated with zinc gluconate glycine lozenges or placebo.

Figure 9. The recovery curves in the Macknin (1998) trial with children.

In Analysis 9.1, Nault used SD = 2.8 days in the placebo group and SD = 8.5 days in the zinc group [23, p.163]; see Figure 1 of this document. However, the distributions are closely similar and thus there cannot be 3-fold difference in the SD in the two groups. Nault does not describe what is the source for the SD values in the Analysis 9.1.

Nault also reports the age in the Macknin (1998) trial as follows [23, p.83]:

“Age (mean (SD)): 11.67 (7.5)” with the mean and SD identical in zinc and placebo groups.

However, Macknin (1998) trial reports as follows [38, p.1964]:

“Age, median (IQR), y 13 (6-16) [in Placebo] 13 (6-16) [in Zinc]”

Macknin (1998) did not report the mean values and Nault does not describe the source for the medians.

Nault’s **table 1**: Study characteristics.

Descriptions of “setting” are misleading.

Nault states that the “setting” of Al-Nakib (1987), Farr (1987), and Turner (2001) was “community”. However, all these trials were about experimental colds, i.e., colds caused in a laboratory with rhinovirus inoculation (see Table 1 of this document). They were not about colds occurring naturally in the community.

Because experimental colds and natural colds differ substantially, it is essential to analyze them separately; see above. A reasonable column to describe the type of infection is the “settings”, but it is misleading to describe that experimental colds are community colds.

For several trials, Nault writes “Clinic/medical centre” (Belongia 2001; Eby 2006; Godfrey 1992; Kartasurya 2012; Kurugöl 2007; Mossad 2003; Prasad 2008), though the “Clinic/medical centre” was purely a contact place for outpatients with the community-originated common colds. In most other trials the setting was “Community” which more accurately describes that the patients were outpatients from the community. In this respect the descriptions in Nault’s table 1 are inconsistent.

Errors in other Cochrane reviews

Cochrane reviews are often promoted as high-quality systematic reviews that can be trusted:

“Cochrane: Trusted evidence. Informed decisions. Better health.”

<https://www.cochrane.org> (Accessed 2024-9-13).

The Cochrane reviews by Nault et al. (2024) [23] and by Singh and Das (2011/2013/2015) [15,17,19] are not the only Cochrane reviews that have been shown to be flawed and that have misled readers. Given the promises of Cochrane, it is informative to look at certain other Cochrane reviews as they indicate that there may be wider problems in the procedures to review and update the Cochrane reviews.

In 2021, I found flaws in the Cochrane review on *Vitamin C and pneumonia* (2020) [136], which falls within the responsibility of the Cochrane Acute Respiratory Infections group along with the reviews on zinc and the common cold.

For example, the authors of the vitamin C and pneumonia review stated:

We included studies involving: 1. healthy adults and children receiving vitamin C supplementation for the prevention of pneumonia.

However, two trials (Coulehan et al. and Bancalari et al.) were included in the review despite the fact that they were common cold trials and neither mentioned pneumonia even as a secondary outcome [137]. Furthermore, according to the Cochrane review, the number of pneumonia “events” in the Bancalari trial was 21 in each group. However, that was not the number of infections, but the number of children who had ≥ 1 infections. There were 46 infection events in the placebo group (N=30) and 38 in the vitamin C group (N=32). However, none of these 84 respiratory infections was pneumonia; they were the common cold [137,138].

In 2009, I found that there were several errors in the Cochrane review *Vitamin C supplementation for asthma* (2009) [139]. For example, there were errors in data extraction; one trial had 20 participants, but only 11 participants were included in the Cochrane analysis. There were errors in the calculations - the unpaired t-test was used when the paired test should have been used. My feedback was published in the (2010) version of the “2009” review [140,141].

The managing editor of the Cochrane Airways group, Emma Welsh, wrote a response to my criticism in the (2012) version of the “2009” Cochrane review [142]. Simultaneously, the three analysis figures, which were the main focus of my critique, were removed from the review. In their absence, however, my feedback though originally valid became irrelevant. Furthermore, the remaining figures were renumbered so that the figure numbers in my feedback indicated real but different figures; therefore, readers would consider that I was confused. Finally, many responses by Emma Welsh did not seem valid [143]. I contacted David Tovey, Editor-in-Chief of Cochrane, but our correspondence did not lead to any constructive efforts to correct the problem. After a year, I contacted COPE which stated that the original (2009) version [139] must be made available to readers; see a brief summary of the long process [144].

As a result of this process, one single PubMed record (#19160185) links to two different versions of the same “2009” Cochrane review. The PubMedCentral version (2009) includes all the original figures, but not my feedback [139]. The Cochrane Library version (2012) includes my feedback, but does not include the three analysis figures to which my feedback focused [142]. Finally, a third version of the “vitamin C supplementation for asthma” (2010) has both the original figures and my feedback, and is available at the University of Helsinki Open Repository and Zenodo [140]. Furthermore, the errors that I pointed out in 2009 were in existence in the 2001 version of the Cochrane review, so the review had been misleading readers for over a decade [143]. Eventually, the review was withdrawn by Cochrane [145].

In 2019, I found errors in Bonini et al.’s data extraction in the Cochrane review (2013) *Beta₂-agonists for exercise-induced asthma* [146], which also falls within the remit of the Cochrane Airways group. For example, Bronsky (1995) had reported that FEV₁ decline was 6% in two salbutamol groups, whereas in the Cochrane review, Bonini et al. reported FEV₁ decline in those same groups as 16% and 26%. Thus, Bonini had added 10 and 20 percentage points to the original data.

Del Col (1993) had reported FEV₁ declines of 0.76% and 2.37% in two salbutamol groups, whereas in the Cochrane review Bonini et al. here too added 20 and 10 percentage points so that the Cochrane version showed 20.76% and 12.37%. In addition, many data extractions from the placebo groups and β₂-agonist groups were from different time points. See a summary of the errors elsewhere [147,148].

The Cochrane Airways group was informed of the errors in the Bonini (2013) Cochrane review on 11 June 2020:

The review by Bonini et al. has several errors related to data extraction, some of which are particularly large. For example, in the Bronsky (1995) and the Del Col (1993) trials, published FEV₁ declines in the beta₂-agonist tests appear 10 and 20 percentage points higher than in the original studies. There are also several cases of inconsistent data extraction...

<https://www.cochranelibrary.com/cdsr/doi/10.1002/14651858.CD003564.pub3/read-comments> (Accessed 2024-9-13)

However, the errors remain uncorrected in September 2024, which is 4 years after the above comment was posted. Thus, the review procedures of these Cochrane groups are not tight enough to prevent such errors being published, but even when the Cochrane editors are informed of errors, they do not coordinate correction in a timely fashion.

The Cochrane reviews described above and the recent Nault et al. review on zinc and the common cold are not reliable and do not help the reader to draw informed decisions based on evidence.

Several authors have pointed out broader concerns with “Cochrane”, which is no longer named the “Cochrane Collaboration” [149-154].

Acknowledgements

I am grateful to Elizabeth Chalker for critically reading this document.

References

1. Eby GA. Linearity in dose-response from zinc lozenges in treatment of common colds. *Journal of Pharmacy Technology*. 1995;11(3):110-122.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/875512259501100308>
2. Eby GA. Zinc ion availability – the determinant of efficacy in zinc lozenge treatment of common colds. *J Antimicrob Chemother*. 1997;40(4):483-93.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordjournals.jac.a020864>
3. Eby GA. Zinc lozenges: cold cure or candy? Solution chemistry determinations. *Biosci Rep*. 2004;24(1):23-39.
<https://doi.org/10.1023/b:bire.0000037754.71063.41>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7087920>
4. Eby GA. Zinc lozenges as cure for the common cold – a review and hypothesis. *Med Hypotheses*. 2010;74(3):482-92.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mehy.2009.10.017>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7173295>
5. Eby GA. Handbook for Curing the Common Cold. The Zinc Lozenge Story. 1994/2002. Zenodo.
<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11546133>
6. Bakar NKA, Taylor DM, Williams DR. The chemical speciation of zinc in human saliva: possible correlation with reduction of the symptoms of the common cold produced by zinc gluconate containing lozenges. *Chemical Speciation & Bioavailability*. 1999;11:95-101.
<https://doi.org/10.3184/095422999782775672>
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/233706734>
7. Hemilä H. Zinc lozenges may shorten the duration of colds: a systematic review. *Open Respir Med J*. 2011;5:51-8.
<https://doi.org/10.2174/1874306401105010051>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc3136969>
8. Hemilä H. Zinc lozenges and the common cold: a meta-analysis comparing zinc acetate and zinc gluconate, and the role of zinc dosage. *JRSM Open*. 2017;8(5):2054270417694291.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/2054270417694291>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5418896>
9. Hemilä H, Petrus EJ, Fitzgerald JT, Prasad A. Zinc acetate lozenges for treating the common cold: an individual patient data meta-analysis. *Br J Clin Pharmacol*. 2016;82(5):1393-8.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/bcp.13057>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc5061795>
10. Hemilä H, Fitzgerald JT, Petrus EJ, Prasad A. Zinc acetate lozenges may improve the recovery rate of common cold patients: an individual patient data meta-analysis. *Open Forum Infect Dis*. 2017;4(2):ofx059.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/ofid/ofx059>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5410113>
11. Hemilä H, Chalker E. The effectiveness of high dose zinc acetate lozenges on various common cold symptoms: a meta-analysis. *BMC Fam Pract*. 2015;16:24.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12875-015-0237-6>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc4359576>
12. Hemilä H, Chalker E, Tukiainen J. Quantile treatment effect of zinc lozenges on common cold duration: a novel approach to analyze the effect of treatment on illness duration. *Front Pharmacol*. 2022;13:817522.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2022.817522>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8844493>
13. Hemilä H, Chalker E, Tukiainen J. Response: Commentary: Quantile treatment effect of zinc lozenges on common cold duration: a novel approach to analyze the effect of treatment on illness duration. *Front Pharmacol*. 2024;15:1335784.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2024.1335784>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC11035776>
14. Hemilä H, Pirinen M. Estimating quantile treatment effect on the original scale of the outcome variable: a case study of common cold treatments. *Arxiv*. 2023 Oct.
<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2310.17917>
<https://arxiv.org/abs/2310.17917>
15. Singh M, Das RR. Zinc for the common cold. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2011;(2):CD001364.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.cd001364.pub3>

16. Hemilä H. The zinc for the common cold review by Singh and Das has a number of problems which should be considered when the review is next time updated. University of Helsinki Open Repository, 2011.
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/39188>
<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10854101>
17. Singh M, Das RR. Zinc for the common cold. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2013;(6):CD001364.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.cd001364.pub4>
18. Hemilä H. Concerns about unattributed copying of text and data, and about numerous other problems in the Cochrane review “Zinc for the Common Cold” by Singh M, Das RR (2013). University of Helsinki Open Repository, 2015.
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/153180>
<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.6394115>
19. Singh M, Das RR. **WITHDRAWN**: Zinc for the common cold. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2015;2015(4):CD001364.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.cd001364.pub5>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc6457799>
20. Hemilä H. Problems with the calculations in the JAMA Clinical Evidence Synopsis “Oral Zinc for the Common Cold” by Das and Singh (2014). University of Helsinki Open Repository, 2015.
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/153617>
<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.6393781>
21. Hemilä H. Common cold treatment using zinc. *JAMA.* 2015;314(7):730.
<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2015.8174>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/223757>
22. Das RR, Singh M. Notice of **Retraction**: Das RR, Singh M. Oral zinc for the common cold. *JAMA.* 2014;311(14):1440-1441. *JAMA.* 2016;316(24):2678.
<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2016.18134>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28027374>
23. Nault D, Machingo TA, Shipper AG, Antiporta DA, Hamel C, Nourouzpour S, Konstantinidis M, Phillips E, Lipski EA, Wieland LS. Zinc for prevention and treatment of the common cold. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2024 May 9;5(5):CD014914.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.cd014914.pub2>
24. Hemilä H, Herman ZS. Vitamin C and the common cold: a retrospective analysis of Chalmers’ review. *J Am Coll Nutr.* 1995;14(2):116-23.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/07315724.1995.10718483>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/42358>
25. Friedrich JO, Adhikari NK, Beyene J. Ratio of means for analyzing continuous outcomes in meta-analysis performed as well as mean difference methods. *J Clin Epidemiol.* 2011;64(5):556-64.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2010.09.016>
26. Hemilä H. Many continuous variables such as the duration of the common cold should be analyzed using the relative scale. *J Clin Epidemiol.* 2016;78:128-9.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2016.03.020>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/173096>
27. Hemilä H. Duration of the common cold and similar continuous outcomes should be analyzed on the relative scale: a case study of two zinc lozenge trials. *BMC Med Res. Methodol.* 2017;17(1):82.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-017-0356-y>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5427521>
28. Hemilä H, Friedrich JO. Many continuous variables should be analyzed using the relative scale: a case study of β_2 -agonists for preventing exercise-induced bronchoconstriction. *Syst Rev.* 2019;8(1):282.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-019-1183-5>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6865024>
29. Douglas RM, Hemilä H, D’Souza R, Chalker EB, Treacy B. Vitamin C for preventing and treating the common cold. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2004;(4):CD000980.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.cd000980.pub2>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/228061>
30. Douglas RM, Hemilä H, Chalker E, Treacy B. Vitamin C for preventing and treating the common cold. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2007;(3):CD000980.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.cd000980.pub3>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/318164>

31. Shamseer L, Vohra S, Bax R, Spee L, Madderom M, Hemilä H. Commentaries on “Vitamin C for preventing and treating the common cold” with responses from the review author. *Evid Based Child Health: A Cochrane Rev J*. 2008;3:723–8.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/ebch.261>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/228088>
32. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Vitamin C for preventing and treating the common cold. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2013;2013(1):CD000980.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.cd000980.pub4>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8078152>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/225864>
33. Hirt M, Nobel S, Barron E. Zinc nasal gel for the treatment of common cold symptoms: a double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. *Ear Nose Throat J*. 2000;79(10):778-80,782.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/014556130007901008>
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/12271808>
34. Belongia EA, Berg R, Liu K. A randomized trial of zinc nasal spray for the treatment of upper respiratory illness in adults. *Am J Med*. 2001;111(2):103-8.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0002-9343\(01\)00765-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0002-9343(01)00765-3)
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/11846898>
35. Mossad SB. Effect of zincum gluconicum nasal gel on the duration and symptom severity of the common cold in otherwise healthy adults. *QJM*. 2003;96(1):35-43.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/qjmed/hcg004>
36. Godfrey JC, Conant Sloane B, Smith DS, Turco JH, Mercer N, Godfrey NJ. Zinc gluconate and the common cold: a controlled clinical study. *J Int Med Res*. 1992;20(3):234-46.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/030006059202000305>
37. Petrus EJ, Lawson KA, Bucci LR, Blum K. Randomized, double-masked, placebo-controlled clinical study of the effectiveness of zinc acetate lozenges on common cold symptoms in allergy-tested subjects. *Curr Ther Res Clin Exp*. 1998;59(9):595-607.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0011-393x\(98\)85058-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0011-393x(98)85058-3)
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc7118419>
38. Macknin ML, Piedmonte M, Calendine C, Janosky J, Wald E. Zinc gluconate lozenges for treating the common cold in children: a randomized controlled trial. *JAMA*. 1998;279(24):1962-7.
<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.279.24.1962>
39. Prasad AS, Fitzgerald JT, Bao B, Beck FW, Chandrasekar PH. Duration of symptoms and plasma cytokine levels in patients with the common cold treated with zinc acetate. A randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. *Ann Intern Med*. 2000;133(4):245-52.
<https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-133-4-200008150-00006>
40. Prasad AS, Beck FW, Bao B, Snell D, Fitzgerald JT. Duration and severity of symptoms and levels of plasma interleukin-1 receptor antagonist, soluble tumor necrosis factor receptor, and adhesion molecules in patients with common cold treated with zinc acetate. *J Infect Dis*. 2008;197(6):795-802.
<https://doi.org/10.1086/528803>
41. Tisdall FF, Brown A, Defries RD. Persistent anosmia following zinc sulfate nasal spraying. *J Pediatr*. 1938;18(13):60-2.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-3476\(38\)80128-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-3476(38)80128-1)
42. Jafek BW, Linschoten MR, Murrow BW. Anosmia after intranasal zinc gluconate use. *Am J Rhinol*. 2004;18(3):137-41.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/194589240401800302>
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/8427447>
43. Alexander TH, Davidson TM. Intranasal zinc and anosmia: the zinc-induced anosmia syndrome. *Laryngoscope*. 2006;116(2):217-220.
<https://doi.org/10.1097/01.mlg.0000191549.17796.13>
 See discussion; 2006;116(9):
<https://doi.org/10.1097/01.mlg.0000231311.68800.57> Seidman MD, p.1720-1.
<https://doi.org/10.1097/01.mlg.0000231313.29500.f2> Davidson TM, p.1721-2.
<https://doi.org/10.1097/01.mlg.0000230480.67612.38> Jafek BW, p.1722-3.
44. Davidson TM, Smith WM. The Bradford Hill criteria and zinc-induced anosmia: a causality analysis. *Arch Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg*. 2010;136(7):673-6.
<https://doi.org/10.1001/archoto.2010.111>
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/45275223>

45. Mossad SB, Macknin ML, Medendorp SV, Mason P. Zinc gluconate lozenges for treating the common cold. A randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled study. *Ann Intern Med.* 1996;125(2):81-8. <https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-125-2-199607150-00001>
46. Hemilä H. Vitamin C supplementation and common cold symptoms: factors affecting the magnitude of the benefit. *Med Hypotheses.* 1999;52(2):171-8. <https://doi.org/10.1054/mehy.1997.0639>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/223761>
47. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Vitamin C reduces the severity of common colds: a meta-analysis. *BMC Public Health.* 2023;23(1):2468. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-023-17229-8>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC10712193>
48. R Core Team. *R Project for Statistical Computing.* <https://www.r-project.org> (Accessed 2024-9-13).
49. Schwarzer G, Carpenter JR, Rucker G. *Meta-analysis with R.* London: Springer (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-21416-0>
50. Balduzzi S, Rücker G, Schwarzer G. How to perform a meta-analysis with R: a practical tutorial. *Evid Based Ment Health.* 2019;22:153–60. <https://doi.org/10.1136/ebmental-2019-300117>
51. NIH. Background Information: Dietary Supplements. <https://ods.od.nih.gov/factsheets/DietarySupplements-Consumer> (Accessed 2024-9-13)
52. FDA. What is a dietary supplement? <https://www.fda.gov/food/information-consumers-using-dietary-supplements/questions-and-answers-dietary-supplements> (Accessed 2024-9-14)
53. Eby GA, Davis DR, Halcomb WW. Reduction in duration of common colds by zinc gluconate lozenges in a double-blind study. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother.* 1984;25(1):20-4. <https://doi.org/10.1128/aac.25.1.20>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC185426>
54. Farr BM, Conner EM, Betts RF, Oleske J, Minnefor A, Gwaltney JM Jr. Two randomized controlled trials of zinc gluconate lozenge therapy of experimentally induced rhinovirus colds. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother.* 1987;31(8):1183-7. <https://doi.org/10.1128/aac.31.8.1183>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC174900>
55. Godfrey JC. Zinc for the common cold. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother.* 1988;32(4):605-6. <https://doi.org/10.1128/aac.32.4.605>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc172232>
56. Eby GA. Stability constants of zinc complexes affect common cold treatment results. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother.* 1988;32(4):606-7. <https://doi.org/10.1128/aac.32.4.606>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC172233>
57. Martin RB. pH as a variable in free zinc ion concentration from zinc-containing lozenges. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother.* 1988;32(4):608-9. <https://doi.org/10.1128/aac.32.4.608>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc172234>
58. Zarembo JE, Godfrey JC, Godfrey NJ. Zinc(II) in saliva: determination of concentrations produced by different formulations of zinc gluconate lozenges containing common excipients. *J Pharm Sci.* 1992;81(2):128-30. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jps.2600810205>
59. Institute of Medicine (US) Panel on Micronutrients. Dietary Reference Intakes for Vitamin A, Vitamin K, Arsenic, Boron, Chromium, Copper, Iodine, Iron, Manganese, Molybdenum, Nickel, Silicon, Vanadium, and Zinc. Washington (DC): National Academies Press (US); 2001. Chapter 12, pp.442-501. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK222317>
<https://nap.nationalacademies.org/read/10026/chapter/14>
<https://doi.org/10.17226/10026>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK222310>
60. Douglas RM, Miles HB, Moore BW, Ryan P, Pinnock CB. Failure of effervescent zinc acetate lozenges to alter the course of upper respiratory tract infections in Australian adults. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother.* 1987;31(8):1263-5. <https://doi.org/10.1128/aac.31.8.1263>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc174915>

61. Smith DS, Helzner EC, Nuttall CE Jr, Collins M, Rofman BA, Ginsberg D, Goswick CB, Magner A. Failure of zinc gluconate in treatment of acute upper respiratory tract infections. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother.* 1989;33(5):646-8.
<https://doi.org/10.1128/aac.33.5.646>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc172506>
62. Al-Nakib W, Higgins PG, Barrow I, Batstone G, Tyrrell DA. Prophylaxis and treatment of rhinovirus colds with zinc gluconate lozenges. *J Antimicrob Chemother.* 1987;20(6):893-901.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/jac/20.6.893>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc7110079>
63. Turner RB, Cetnarowski WE. Effect of treatment with zinc gluconate or zinc acetate on experimental and natural colds. *Clin Infect Dis.* 2000;31(5):1202-8.
<https://doi.org/10.1086/317437>
64. Eby GA. Elimination of efficacy by additives in zinc acetate lozenges for common colds. *Clin Infect Dis.* 2001;32(10):1520.
<https://doi.org/10.1086/320177>
65. Eby GA, Halcomb WW. Ineffectiveness of zinc gluconate nasal spray and zinc orotate lozenges in common-cold treatment: a double-blind, placebo-controlled clinical trial. *Altern Ther Health Med.* 2006;12(1):34-8.
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/7320391>
<https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/pdf/0b25bc6be008166ff8b51787d00b451e807f55ba>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/16454145>
66. Hemilä H, Haukka J, Alho M, Vahtera J, Kivimäki M. Zinc acetate lozenges for the treatment of the common cold: a randomised controlled trial. *BMJ Open.* 2020;10(1):e031662.
<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2019-031662>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc7045205>
67. Eby G. Zinc lozenges as a common cold treatment [Non-functional lozenges on the market]. 2014.
<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11616037>
68. Weismann K, Jakobsen JP, Weismann JE, Hammer UM, Nyholm SM, Hansen B, Lomholt KE, Schmidt K. Zinc gluconate lozenges for common cold. A double-blind clinical trial. *Dan Med Bull.* 1990;37(3):279-81.
<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11544824>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/2192839>
69. Kurugöl Z, Akilli M, Bayram N, Koturoglu G. The prophylactic and therapeutic effectiveness of zinc sulphate on common cold in children. *Acta Paediatr.* 2006;95(10):1175-81.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/08035250600603024>
70. Kurugöl Z, Bayram N, Atik T. Effect of zinc sulfate on common cold in children: randomized, double blind study. *Pediatr Int.* 2007;49(6):842-7.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1442-200x.2007.02448.x>
71. Vakili R, Vahedian M, Khodaei G, Mahmoudi M. Effects of zinc supplementation in occurrence and duration of common cold in school aged children during cold season: a double blind placebo-controlled trial. *Iranian Journal of Pediatrics.* 2009;19(4):376-80.
<https://www.sid.ir/paper/76011/en>
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/43559997>
72. Rerksuppaphol S, Rerksuppaphol L. A randomized controlled trial of chelated zinc for prevention of the common cold in Thai school children. *Paediatr Int Child Health.* 2013;33(3):145-50.
<https://doi.org/10.1179/2046905513y.0000000064>
73. Sánchez J, Villada OA, Rojas ML, Montoya L, Díaz A, Vargas C, Chica J, Herrera AA. Efecto del zinc aminoquelado y el sulfato de zinc en la incidencia de la infección respiratoria y la diarrea en niños preescolares de centros infantiles [Effect of zinc amino acid chelate and zinc sulfate in the incidence of respiratory infection and diarrhea among preschool children in child daycare centers]. *Biomedica.* 2014;34(1):79-91.
<https://doi.org/10.7705/biomedica.v34i1.1581>
http://www.scielo.org.co/scielo.php?script=sci_abstract&pid=S0120-41572014000100011
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/273990122>
74. Somé JW, Abbeddou S, Yakes Jimenez E, Hess SY, Ouédraogo ZP, Guissou RM, Vosti SA, Ouédraogo JB, Brown KH. Effect of zinc added to a daily small-quantity lipid-based nutrient supplement on diarrhoea, malaria, fever and respiratory infections in young children in rural Burkina Faso: a cluster-randomised trial. *BMJ Open.* 2015;5(9):e007828.
<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2015-007828>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc4567679>

75. Turner RB. Ineffectiveness of intranasal zinc gluconate for prevention of experimental rhinovirus colds. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2001;33(11):1865-70.
<https://doi.org/10.1086/324347>
76. Rao SS, Hendley JO, Hayden FG, Gwaltney JM. Symptom expression in natural and experimental rhinovirus colds. *Am J Rhinol*. 1995;9(1):49-52.
<https://doi.org/10.2500/105065895781874114>
77. Turner RB, Witek TJ, Riker DK. Comparison of symptom severity in natural and experimentally induced colds. *Am J Rhinol*. 1996;10(3):167-72.
<https://doi.org/10.2500/105065896781794888>
78. Chalmers TC, Celano P, Sacks HS, Smith H Jr. Bias in treatment assignment in controlled clinical trials. *N Engl J Med*. 1983;309(22):1358-61.
<https://doi.org/10.1056/nejm198312013092204>
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/16561928>
79. Malik A, Taneja DK, Devasenapathy N, Rajeshwari K. Zinc supplementation for prevention of acute respiratory infections in infants: a randomized controlled trial. *Indian Pediatr*. 2014;51(10):780-4.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s13312-014-0503-z>
80. Higgins JPT, Thomas J, Chandler J, Cumpston M, Li T, Page MJ, Welch VA (editors). *Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions* version 6.4 (updated Aug 2023). Cochrane, 2023.
<https://training.cochrane.org/handbook/current/chapter-08#section-8-7>
<https://training.cochrane.org/handbook/current/chapter-02> (Accessed 2024-9-13)
81. Meinert CL. *Clinical Trials: Design, Conduct, and Analysis*. Oxford, 1986, pp.276-277.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780195035681.003.0026>
82. Mathis S, Le Masson G, Soulages A, Duval F, Carla L, Vallat JM, Solé G. Olfaction and anosmia: From ancient times to COVID-19. *J Neurol Sci*. 2021;425:117433.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jns.2021.117433>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC9755649>
83. Suzuki M, Saito K, Min WP, Vladau C, Toida K, Itoh H, Murakami S. Identification of viruses in patients with postviral olfactory dysfunction. *Laryngoscope*. 2007;117(2):272-7.
<https://doi.org/10.1097/01.mlg.0000249922.37381.1e>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7165544>
84. Tian J, Pinto JM, Li L, Zhang S, Sun Z, Wei Y. Identification of viruses in patients with postviral olfactory dysfunction by multiplex reverse-transcription polymerase chain reaction. *Laryngoscope*. 2021;131(1):158-64.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/lary.28997>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7436707>
85. Akerlund A, Bende M, Murphy C. Olfactory threshold and nasal mucosal changes in experimentally induced common cold. *Acta Otolaryngol*. 1995;115(1):88-92.
<https://doi.org/10.3109/00016489509133353>
86. Sudre CH, Keshet A, Graham MS, et al. Anosmia, ageusia, and other COVID-19-like symptoms in association with a positive SARS-CoV-2 test, across six national digital surveillance platforms: an observational study. *Lancet Digit Health*. 2021;3(9):e577-e586.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/s2589-7500\(21\)00115-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2589-7500(21)00115-1)
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8297994>
87. Doty RL. The mechanisms of smell loss after SARS-CoV-2 infection. *Lancet Neurol*. 2021;20(9):693-5.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/s1474-4422\(21\)00202-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1474-4422(21)00202-7)
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8324112>
88. Rothman KJ, Greenland S. Causation and causal inference in epidemiology. *Am J Public Health*. 2005;95 Suppl 1:S144-50.
<https://doi.org/10.2105/ajph.2004.059204>
89. Rothman KJ. The wrong message from the wrong talk. *Observational Studies*. 2020;6(2):30-2.
<https://doi.org/10.1353/obs.2020.0006>
<https://muse.jhu.edu/pub/56/article/793347/summary>
90. Pories WJ, Henzel JH, Rob CG, Strain WH. Acceleration of healing with zinc sulfate. *Ann Surg*. 1967;165:432-6.
<https://doi.org/10.1097/00000658-196703000-00015>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc1617499>
91. Barcia PJ. Lack of acceleration of healing with zinc sulfate. *Ann Surg*. 1970;172:1048-50.
<https://doi.org/10.1097/00000658-197012000-00019>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc1397149>

92. Serjeant GR, Galloway R, Gueri M. Oral zinc sulphate in sickle-cell ulcers. *Lancet*. 1970;2:891-2.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(70\)92067-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(70)92067-2)
93. Greaves MW, Skillen AW. Effects of long-continued ingestion of zinc sulphate in patients with venous leg ulceration. *Lancet*. 1970;2:889-91.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(70\)92066-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(70)92066-0)
94. Hallböök T, Laner E. Serum-zinc and healing of venous leg ulcers. *Lancet*. 1972;2:780-2.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(72\)92143-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(72)92143-5)
95. Czerwinski AW, Clark ML, Serafetinides EA, Perrier C, Huber W. Safety and efficacy of zinc sulfate in geriatric patients. *Clin Pharmacol Ther*. 1974;15(4):436-41.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/cpt1974154436>
96. Simkin PA. Oral zinc sulphate in rheumatoid arthritis. *Lancet*. 1976;2:539-42.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(76\)91793-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(76)91793-1)
97. Lyckholm L, Hedding SP, Parker G, et al. A randomized, placebo controlled trial of oral zinc for chemotherapy-related taste and smell disorders. *J Pain Palliat Care Pharmacother*. 2012;26:111-4.
<https://doi.org/10.3109/15360288.2012.676618>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc4042409>
98. Bamford JT, Gessert CE, Haller IV, Kruger K, Johnson BP. Randomized, double-blind trial of 220 mg zinc sulfate twice daily in the treatment of rosacea. *Int J Dermatol*. 2012;51:459-62.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-4632.2011.05353.x>
99. Hadwan MH, Almashhedy LA, Als Salman AR. Oral zinc supplementation restores high molecular weight seminal zinc binding protein to normal value in Iraqi infertile men. *BMC Urol*. 2012;12:32.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2490-12-32>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc3503568>
100. Ala A, Walker AP, Ashkan K, Dooley JS, Schilsky ML. Wilson's disease. *Lancet*. 2007;369(9559):397-408.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(07\)60196-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(07)60196-2)
101. Członkowska A, Litwin T, Dusek P, Ferenci P, Lutsenko S, Medici V, Rybakowski JK, Weiss KH, Schilsky ML. Wilson disease. *Nat Rev Dis Primers*. 2018;4(1):21.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41572-018-0018-3>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc6416051>
102. Brewer GJ, Askari FK. Wilson's disease: clinical management and therapy. *J Hepatol*. 2005;42 (Suppl 1):S13-S21.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhep.2004.11.013>
103. Hoogenraad TU. Zinc treatment of Wilson's disease. *J Lab Clin Med*. 1998;132:240-1.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0022-2143\(98\)90034-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0022-2143(98)90034-8)
104. Marcellini M, Di Ciommo V, Callea F, Devito R, Comparcola D, Sartorelli MR, Carelli G, Nobili V. Treatment of Wilson's disease with zinc from the time of diagnosis in pediatric patients: a single-hospital, 10-year follow-up study. *J Lab Clin Med*. 2005;145(3):139-43.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lab.2005.01.007>
105. Cochrane Library. What is PICO.
<https://www.cochranelibrary.com/about-pico> (Accessed 2024-9-13)
106. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Abrupt termination of vitamin C from ICU patients may increase mortality: secondary analysis of the LOVIT trial. *Eur J Clin Nutr*. 2023;77(4):490-4.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41430-022-01254-8>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc10115628>
107. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Rebound effect explains the divergence in survival after 5 days in a controlled trial on vitamin C for COVID-19 patients. *Front. Med*. 2024;11:1391346.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2024.1391346>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc11151746>
108. Hemilä H. Vitamin C supplementation and common cold symptoms: problems with inaccurate reviews. *Nutrition* 1996;12:804-9.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0899-9007\(96\)00223-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0899-9007(96)00223-7)
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/225877>
109. Hemilä H. Vitamin C, the placebo effect, and the common cold: a case study of how preconceptions influence the analysis of results. *J Clin Epidemiol*. 1996;49(10):1079-84.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/0895-4356\(96\)00189-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0895-4356(96)00189-8)
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/225872>
110. Hemilä H. To the dissent by Thomas Chalmers. *J Clin Epidemiol*. 1996;49(10):1087.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/0895-4356\(96\)00191-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0895-4356(96)00191-6)
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/225873>

111. Hemilä H. Do Vitamins C and E Affect Respiratory Infections? Ph.D. Thesis. University of Helsinki, Helsinki, Finland, 2006.
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/20335>
<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.6395595>
112. Hemilä H. The role of vitamin C in the treatment of the common cold. *Am Fam Physician*. 2007;76(8):1111, 1115.
<https://www.aafp.org/pubs/afp/issues/2007/1015/p1111a.html>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/17992770>
113. Hemilä H. Vitamin C for the common cold should not be rejected on the basis of old and erroneous articles. *J Allergy Clin Immunol*. 2009;124(4):859.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaci.2009.06.015>
114. Hemilä H. Randomised trials on vitamin C. *Br J Nutr*. 2011;105(3):485-7.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/s000711451000351x>
115. Hemilä H. The effect of vitamin C on the common cold. *J Pharm Pract*. 2011;24(2):241-2.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0897190010392376>
116. Louhiala P, Hemilä H. Can CAM treatments be evidence-based? *Focus Altern. Complement Ther*. 2014;19:84-9.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/fct.12110>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/228056>
117. Hemilä H. Thomas Chalmers, vitamin C and the common cold. *J R Soc Med*. 2016;109(2):46.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0141076815606279>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4793763>
118. Hemilä H. Vitamin C in clinical therapeutics. *Clin Ther*. 2017;39(10):2110-2.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clinthera.2017.08.005>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/228957>
119. Hemilä H, Carr A, Chalker E. Vitamin C may increase the recovery rate of outpatient cases of SARS-CoV-2 infection by 70%: reanalysis of the COVID A to Z randomized clinical trial. *Front Immunol*. 2021;12:674681.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2021.674681>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8141621>
120. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Vitamin C and zinc lozenges for COVID-19? *J Am Pharm Assoc*. 2021;61(5):e39.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.japh.2021.05.018>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8163692>
121. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Commentary: The long history of vitamin C: from prevention of the common cold to potential aid in the treatment of COVID-19. *Front Immunol*. 2021;12:659001.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2021.659001>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8047412>
122. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Bias against vitamin C in mainstream medicine: examples from trials of vitamin C for infections. *Life (Basel)* 2022;12(1):62.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/life12010062>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc8779885>
123. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Assessment of vitamin C effects on pneumonia and COVID-19 using Mendelian randomization: analysis may be misleading. *Eur J Clin Nutr* 2022;76(9):1347-8.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41430-022-01091-9>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8853427>
124. Pauling L. Ascorbic acid and the common cold. *Am J Clin Nutr*. 1971;24(11):1294-9.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/ajcn/24.11.1294>
125. Pauling L. Ascorbic acid and the common cold: Evaluation of its efficacy and toxicity. Part I. *Medical Tribune*. 1976;17:18-9.
<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11546757>
126. Pauling L. Ascorbic acid and the common cold. Part II. *Medical Tribune*. 1976;17:37-8.
<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11547088>
127. Pauling L. Medical establishment and vitamin C. *In: Vitamin C, the Common Cold, and the Flu*. Freeman; San Francisco, CA, USA, 1976, pp.121–138.
128. Pauling L. Organized medicine and the vitamins. *In: How to Live Longer and Feel Better*. Freeman; San Francisco, CA, USA, 1986, pp.225–236.

129. Fazekas T, Eickhoff P, Pruckner N, Vollnhofer G, Fischmeister G, Diakos C, Rauch M, Verdianz M, Zoubek A, Gadner H, Lion T. Lessons learned from a double-blind randomised placebo-controlled study with a iota-carrageenan nasal spray as medical device in children with acute symptoms of common cold. *BMC Complement Altern Med.* 2012;12:147.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6882-12-147>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc3575307>
130. Ludwig M, Enzenhofer E, Schneider S, Rauch M, Bodenteich A, Neumann K, Prieschl-Grassauer E, Grassauer A, Lion T, Mueller CA. Efficacy of a carrageenan nasal spray in patients with common cold: a randomized controlled trial. *Respir Res.* 2013;14(1):124.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/1465-9921-14-124>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc3840586>
131. Eccles R, Meier C, Jawad M, Weinmüller R, Grassauer A, Prieschl-Grassauer E. Efficacy and safety of an antiviral iota-carrageenan nasal spray: a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled exploratory study in volunteers with early symptoms of the common cold. *Respir Res.* 2010;11(1):108.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/1465-9921-11-108>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2923116>
132. Eccles R, Winther B, Johnston SL, Robinson P, Trampisch M, Koelsch S. Efficacy and safety of iota-carrageenan nasal spray versus placebo in early treatment of the common cold in adults: the ICICC trial. *Respir Res.* 2015;16:121.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12931-015-0281-8>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4595062>
133. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Carrageenan nasal spray may double the rate of recovery from coronavirus and influenza virus infections: Re-analysis of randomized trial data. *Pharmacol Res Perspect.* 2021;9(4):e00810.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/prp2.810>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8204093>
134. Koenighofer M, Lion T, Bodenteich A, Prieschl-Grassauer E, Grassauer A, Unger H, Mueller CA, Fazekas T. Carrageenan nasal spray in virus confirmed common cold: individual patient data analysis of two randomized controlled trials. *Multidiscip Respir Med.* 2014;9(1):57.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/2049-6958-9-57>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4236476>
135. Eby GA. Therapeutic effectiveness of ionic zinc for common colds. *Clin Infect Dis.* 2008;46(3):483-4.
<https://doi.org/10.1086/527479>
136. Padhani ZA, Moazzam Z, Ashraf A, Bilal H, Salam RA, Das JK, Bhutta ZA. Vitamin C supplementation for prevention and treatment of pneumonia. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2020;4(4):CD013134.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.cd013134.pub2>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7192369>
137. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Commentary: Vitamin C supplementation for prevention and treatment of pneumonia. *Front Med (Lausanne).* 2021;7:595988.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2020.595988>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc7854566>
Supplement with the details of the problems:
<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fmed.2020.595988/full#supplementary-material>
138. Hemilä H, Chalker E. Vitamin C supplementation for prevention and treatment of pneumonia (2020) [Shortcomings in a Cochrane review]. Zenodo
<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11621606>
139. Kaur B, Rowe BH, Arnold E. Vitamin C supplementation for asthma. [2009 version; all figures present, no feedback by Hemilä]. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2009;CD000993.
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6176494>
140. Kaur B, Rowe BH, Arnold E. Vitamin C supplementation for asthma. [2010 version; both the feedback by Hemilä and all the original figures; the feedback is on p.27]. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2009;CD000993.
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/296440>
<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10853677>
141. Hemilä H. Vitamin C supplementation for asthma [Feedback separately] version 2010. University of Helsinki Open Repository, 2010.
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/296440>
<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.6405775>

142. Kaur B, Rowe BH, Stovold E. Vitamin C supplementation for asthma. [2012 version; feedback by Hemilä present, 3 figures removed]. Cochrane Database Syst Rev. 2009;CD000993. <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD000993.pub3> <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10959542>
143. Hemilä H. Vitamin C and exercise-induced bronchoconstriction: further problems in the Cochrane review “vitamin C for asthma”. University of Helsinki Open Repository, 2013. <https://hdl.handle.net/10138/40816> <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.6405803>
144. Hemilä H. Cochrane has not consistently followed the COPE guidelines. Eur J Clin Invest. 2020;50(4):e13216. <https://doi.org/10.1111/eci.13216> <https://hdl.handle.net/10138/326823>
145. Kaur B, Rowe BH, Stovold E. **WITHDRAWN**: Vitamin C supplementation for asthma. Cochrane Database Syst Rev. 2013 Oct 23;2013(10):CD000993. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24155047> <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD000993.pub4> <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6176495>
146. Bonini M, Di Mambro C, Calderon MA, Compalati E, Schünemann H, Durham S, Canonica GW. Beta₂-agonists for exercise-induced asthma. Cochrane Database Syst Rev. 2013;(10):CD003564. <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.cd003564.pub3> <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC11348701>
147. Hemilä H, Friedrich JO. Many continuous variables should be analyzed using the relative scale: a case study of β₂-agonists for preventing exercise-induced bronchoconstriction. Syst Rev. 2019;8(1):282. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-019-1183-5>
Additional file 1 describes the errors in the Bonini (2013) Cochrane review, pp. 12-15: https://static-content.springer.com/esm/art%3A10.1186%2Fs13643-019-1183-5/MediaObjects/13643_2019_1183_MOESM1_ESM.pdf
148. Hemilä H. Beta₂-agonists for exercise-induced bronchoconstriction: data extraction inconsistencies and errors in the Cochrane review by Bonini et al. (2013). Zenodo 2024. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10959750>
149. Ioannidis JPA. Cochrane crisis: secrecy, intolerance and evidence-based values. Eur J Clin Invest. 2019;49(3):e13058. <https://doi.org/10.1111/eci.13058> <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30520025>
150. Newman M. Has Cochrane lost its way? BMJ. 2019;364:k5302. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.k5302>
Clarification: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.l670>
151. Jørgensen L, Gøtzsche PC, Jefferson T. The Cochrane HPV vaccine review was incomplete and ignored important evidence of bias. BMJ Evid Based Med. 2018;23(5):165-8. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjebm-2018-111012>
152. Gøtzsche PC. What is the moral collapse in the Cochrane Collaboration about? Indian J Med Ethics. 2019;4 (NS)(4):303-309. <https://doi.org/10.20529/ijme.2019.064> <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31791931>
153. Vesper I. Mass resignation guts board of prestigious Cochrane Collaboration. Nature 2018-9-17. <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-018-06727-0> (Accessed 2024-9-13)
154. Nass M, Noble JH Jr. Whither Cochrane? Indian J Med Ethics. 2018;4(1):1-5. <https://doi.org/10.20529/ijme.2018.092> <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30683645>